

HERCCULES
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Analysis of policy alignment including country case studies

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D8.1 Analysis of policy alignment including country case studies

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ABBREVIATIONS, TERMS AND UNITS

Abbreviations

Bln – Billion

BC – Barcelona Convention

CBAM - Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism

CCS – CO₂ capture and storage

CGS – CO₂ geological storage

CO₂ – carbon dioxide

CCUS – CO₂ capture, utilization and storage

EDGAR – Emissions Database for Global Atmospheric Research

ENI – Italian multinational oil and gas company headquartered in Rome

ESR – Effort Sharing Regulation

EU – European Union

EC – European Commission

EU27 – European Union 27 Member States

EU ETS - EU Emission Trading System

GHG – greenhouse gas

GHGE – greenhouse gas emissions

IMO – The International Maritime Organization

INDC – Intended Nationally Determined Contribution

INECP – Integrate National Energy and Climate Plan

LC – London Convention

LP – London Protocol

LULUCF – Land use, land-use change, and forestry. Defined by the UNFCCC Secretariat as a "greenhouse gas inventory sector that covers emissions and removals of greenhouse gases resulting from direct human-induced land use such as settlements and commercial uses, land-use change, and forestry activities"

MAP – Mediterranean Action Plan

MARPOL – International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships

MED POL – Mediterranean Pollution Assessment and Control Programme

Mln – Million

MRG – Monitoring and Reporting Guidelines

MSR – Market Stability Reserve

NDC – Nationally Determined Contribution

NECP – National Energy and Climate Plan

UNCLOS – United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea

UNFCCC – United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change

Terms

London Protocol – Protocol to the Convention on the Prevention of Marine Pollution by Dumping of Wastes and Other Matter

OSPAR Convention – Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic

Units

CO₂/cap/yr – CO₂ emissions per capita per year

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Gt – gigatonne
GtCO₂e – gigatonne of CO₂ emissions
m – metre
km – kilometre
kt – kilotons
kt CO₂ eq – kilotons in CO₂ equivalent
Mt – million tonnes
Mt CO₂ eq – million tonnes in CO₂ equivalent
Mt/yr – million tonnes per year
t – tonnes
t/yr – tonnes per year

0 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The objective of this report is to make an in-depth analysis of the international and national CCS regulations influencing the implementation of CCUS cluster projects and hubs in the targeted HERCCULES regions, as well as the regulatory situation and the political strategies for implementing integrated-chain CCUS in European, national (Italy and Greece) and regional level, concerning the areas hosting the storage sites.

This report was based on desk research on energy and climate strategies, related political instruments, and (policy) initiatives and actors. It is based on previous research conducted in the European finalized and ongoing projects, national reports to the European Commission (EC), and other recent policy and public documents.

Additionally, qualitative questionnaires with national and regional policymakers from ministries and agencies responsible for national policies, issuing permits for storage sites and funding agencies were collected to identify regulatory gaps and areas for future regulatory activities.

Both Italy and Greece have good prospects for wide industrial implementation of CCUS technology and becoming climate-neutral by 2050. In both countries total CO₂ emissions and emissions per capita significantly decreased by 2022 compared to 1990 and 2005. In Italy total fossil CO₂ emissions decreased from 423.3 Mt in 1990 to 322.95 Mt in 2022, whereas CO₂ emissions per capita decreased from 8.38 t in 2005 (maximum since 1990) to 5.48 tonnes in 2022. In Greece, total fossil CO₂ emissions decreased from 77.9 Mt in 1990 to 56.78 Mt in 2022, whereas CO₂ emissions per capita decreased from 9.17 t in 2005 (maximum since 1990) to 5.14 t in 2022.

Both countries implemented the EU CCS Directive (Directive 2009/31/EC) to the full extent that permitted CO₂ geological storage and recently made some needed updates and changes. However, in Greece there are some areas where additional improvements and regulatory developments should be additionally made, such as transboundary issues and third-party access to the storage sites. Nowadays, Italy seems to find itself in a more advanced situation in terms of international regulations implementation, as it is a Party of the London Protocol and planning to implement an amendment to Article 6, permitting CO₂ export for storage under the seabed. On the other hand, Greece is a party of the London Convention, but not of the Protocol and did not report about any plans in this direction. In the National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP) 2023 Greece reported to the EC ambitious climate targets, that are mostly in line with EC plans, or even higher. In contrast, the Italian NECP 2023, reported some targets that were lower than EC requirements. However, the target for ESR emissions in Greece is lower than the EC requires. Both countries received recommendations to fill the gaps and to make improvements in the final NECP to be submitted in 2024.

While answering questionnaires, six Italian policy makers took part in the survey and in some answers, they were better informed than the two participating policymakers from Greece about international regulations and national issues. A higher percentage of Italian policy makers gave positive answers about possibility to implement industrial scale CCUS and CCS related regulations as compared to negative or uncertain answers.

This report is a first draft produced in the first year of the HERCCULES project including policy and regulatory developments by the end of 2023. A revised and final version is planned for the last year of the project. The results of this report will serve as inputs for T9.3 (Regulations/policies/incentives recommendation definition) of the HERCCULES project.

In detail this policy report addresses the following issues:

- Analysis of the international framework in terms of climate strategies and policy (Chapter 2).
- Brief description of the Multilateral Agreements on Marine Environment (Chapter 3)
- Overview of the European Regulation in relation to CCS (Chapter 4)
- National case studies: Italy and Greece (Chapter 5)
- Overview and analysis of the Italian and Greek policymakers' questionnaires (Chapter 6)
- Report's conclusions.

1 INTRODUCTION

This report is a result of the work planned in task 8.1 Regulatory and Policy Context of work package 8 of the HERCCULES project. The objective of this task is to make an in-depth analysis of the international and national CCS regulations influencing the implementation of CCUS cluster projects and hubs in targeted regions, as well as the regulatory situation and the political strategies for implementing integrated-chain CCUS at European, national (Italy and Greece) and regional level, concerning the areas hosting the storage sites.

The aim is to assess current policies, political strategies, and policy actors, examine policy alignment and potential disparities across scale and space, and identify areas of future regulatory activities.

This task included desk research on energy and climate change policy, related political instruments, (policy) initiatives and actors, built on previous research conducted in the Horizon Europe project Pilot STRATEGY and the H2020 project CLEANKER, as well as on other finished and ongoing projects and the most recent policy and public documents.

Additionally, qualitative questionnaires with national and regional policymakers from ministries and agencies responsible for national policies, issuing permits for storage sites and funding agencies were conducted to identify regulatory gaps and areas for future regulatory activities.

In total six Italian and two Greek stakeholders (policymakers) answered the online questionnaires in autumn-winter 2023. Their answers are included in this report and were used for country profiles for Italy and Greece.

This report is a first draft produced during the first year of the HERCCULES project with available political and regulatory developments by the end of 2023/beginning 2024. A revised and finalized version is planned for the last year of the project (M58, i.e., October 2027). The results of this report will serve as inputs for T9.3 (Regulations/policies/incentives recommendation definition, M56-59) of the HERCCULES project.

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2 CLIMATE STRATEGIES AND POLICIES

2.1 PARIS CLIMATE AGREEMENT AND DUBAI COP28 MAIN RESULTS

The United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) Secretariat is the United Nations body in charge of supporting the global response against the threat of climate change. There are 198 countries – members of the UNFCCC.

The 2015 Paris Climate Agreement was a breakthrough in the development of the climate change mitigation program. It has very strong targets - to limit the global temperatures increase to 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels and to hold the increase in the global average temperature to well below 2°C above pre-industrial levels. Almost all nations participated this time and were asked to reduce CO₂ emissions significantly by 2030 and drastically by 2050. The Paris Agreement requires every nation (whether developed or developing), to take part in saving our environment. This made 196 countries endorse the document right from the beginning. At present 195 countries ratified and only 3 countries (members of UNFCCC) signed, but not ratified (Iran, Libya, and Yemen), responsible for 1.38% of the world's CO₂ emissions (UNFCCC, 2024a).

Implementation of the Paris Agreement requires economic and social transformation, based on the best available science. The Paris Agreement works on a five-year cycle of increasingly ambitious climate action or, ratcheting up - carried out by countries. Since 2020, countries have been submitting to the UNFCCC secretariat their national climate action plans, known as nationally determined contributions (NDCs). Each successive NDC is meant to reflect an increasingly higher degree of ambition compared to the previous version (UNFCCC, 2024b).

Recognizing that accelerated action is required to limit global warming to 1.5°C, the COP27 includes decision asking Parties to re-estimate and increase the 2030 targets in their NDCs to be in line with the Paris Agreement target by the end of 2023, considering different national circumstances.

The United Nations Climate Change Conference (COP28) in Dubai in December 2023 ended with an agreement that signals the “beginning of the end” of the fossil fuel era by laying the groundwork for a rapid, just and equitable transition, underpinned by deep emissions cuts and scaled-up finance. The global stocktake is considered the central outcome of COP28 – as it contains all negotiated elements and can be used by countries to develop stronger climate action plans by 2025.

In Dubai it was understood that to limit global warming to 1.5°C, GHGE must be reduced by 43% by 2030 compared to 2019 levels. The global renewable energy capacity and energy efficiency should be tripled by 2030, as well as reduction in coal power, fossil fuel and an end to fossil fuel subsidies. By 2025, Parties are urged to set aggressive emission reduction targets in their next round of climate action plans (NDCs) consistent with the 1.5°C limit (UNFCCC, 2024c).

2.2 EUROPEAN CLIMATE LAW

The European Climate Law entered into force in July 2021. The [European Climate Law](#) includes the European Green Deal's target to make economy and society in Europe climate neutral by 2050 (European Commission, 2023 a). It also includes an interim target to reduce net GHGE by at least **55% by 2030**, compared to 1990 GHGE. Reaching climate neutrality by 2050 is interpreted by EC as net zero **GHGE** in EU countries. This target could be achieved by reducing GHGE, financially supporting green technologies, and environmental protection. The law aims to implement all the goals to EU national policies to include all economic sectors and society to play active role.

Objectives of the law

- Set the way to meet the 2050 climate neutrality objective using all policies, considering social equality and most economic options.
- To increase EU 2030 target, to make it more ambitious and legally support European Union in reaching climate neutrality by 2050.

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- An increased 2030 climate target to reduce the net GHGE to at least 55% compared to 1990, to contribute to emission reductions and removals.
- To increase the EU's carbon sink using a new and more ambitious LULUCF regulation, proposed by EC in 2021 and entered into force in 2023.
- To set a new climate target for 2040, considering estimated for 2030-2050 GHG budget.
- A set a climate target of negative GHGE after 2050.
- To establish the European Scientific Advisory Board on Climate Change to provide independent scientific advice.
- Stronger support for climate change adaptation and strong coherence of the EU policies with the climate neutrality target.
- To involve all the sectors of economy into specific roadmaps preparation to find their way to climate neutrality.

2.3 NATIONAL, EUROPEAN AND WORLD CO₂ EMISSIONS

In 2022 the EU27 was among six largest GHG emitters in the world (including China, the United States, India, Russia and Brazil). They had together 50.1% of the global population, produced 61.2% of global Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and 61.6% of global GHGE and used 63.4% of the global fossil fuel consumption. In 2022, the share of CO₂ in global GHGE resulting from the combustion of fossil fuels was 71.6% of CH₄ - 21%, and the other part of GHGE included 4.8% of N₂O and 2.6% of F-gases. (EU27 produced for 27% less GHG emissions than in 1990 and contributed 6.7% of global emissions, compared to 14.8% in 1990 (Table 1, Crippa et al, 2023).

In 2022, several EU27 countries decreased their GHGE compared to 2021. The largest increase in 2022 was observed in some countries, including Greece (+3.4%). Germany was the largest emitter in EU27 in 2022 with share in GHGE of 21.9%, the second place had France (12.0%), the third place had Poland (11.2%), and Italy was the fourth largest GHG emitter among EU27 countries (11.0%) followed by Spain (9.2%) (Crippa et al, 2023).

Table 1. CO₂ total emissions in Mt (Crippa et al, 2023, EDGAR, 2023, IEA-EDGAR CO₂, 2023)

Country	1990	2000	2005	2015	2020	2021	2022
Italy, San Marino and the Holy See	424.68	453.63	492.53	353.66	295.13	320.76	322.95
Greece	77.90	96.03	103.61	69.43	52.31	54.17	56.78
EU27	3793.29	3549.16	3672.61	3076.5	2633.49	2824.3	2804.2
Global Total	22516.77	25621	29924.59	36158.84	35944.47	38082.16	38522

CO₂ emissions per capita significantly decreased in EU27 countries in 2022 compared with 1990, including Italy and Greece. In both countries, CO₂ emissions per capita (5.48 t in Italy) and (5.14 t in Greece) are lower than the EU27 average (6.32 t), but higher than the Global Total average (4.84 t) (Table 2).

Table 2. CO₂ emissions per capita, Mt (Crippa et al, 2023, EDGAR, 2023, IEA-EDGAR CO₂, 2023)

Country	1990	2000	2005	2010	2015	2020	2021	2022
Italy, San Marino and the Holy See	7.43	7.92	8.38	7.08	5.94	4.99	5.43	5.48
Greece	7.60	8.62	9.17	7.78	6.19	4.71	4.89	5.14
EU27	9.03	8.28	8.44	7.72	6.96	5.94	6.37	6.32
Global Total	4.22	4.17	4.58	4.87	4.90	4.61	4.84	4.84

2.4 THE NATIONALLY DETERMINED CONTRIBUTION OF THE EUROPEAN UNION AND ITS MEMBER STATES

An update of the Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) of the EU and its Member States was submitted to the UNFCCC secretariat in October 2023 by Spain and EC on behalf of the European Union and its Member States (Spain and European Commission, 2023). The NDC includes three parts: (1) an overview, (2) the EU's updated Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) and (3) the Information provided to facilitate Clarity, Transparency and Understanding (ICTU) of the NDC.

The overview named "Summary of Procedural Developments" includes 27 paragraphs. Among the last EU developments are mentioned the European Climate Law, adopted in July 2021, adopted the "Fit for 55" number of proposals aimed to revise and update EU regulations to ensure that EU policies are corresponding to the climate targets of the European Climate Law, the legislative framework necessary to implement the "Fit for 55" and the agreed legislation published in the official Journal of the EU in 2023.

The main domestic policies adopted because of the new climate target agreed in December 2020 are summarized in paragraphs 11-27 of parts (1) and (3) of this document. In these paragraphs a lot of attention is given to EU ETS, ESR and LULUCF stating that emissions reduction targets under the EU legislation are covered by the EU Emissions Trading System (EU ETS), the Effort Sharing Regulation (ESR), and the regulation on land-use related emissions and removals (LULUCF). The EU ETS, which is operated since 2005, introduced a carbon price by setting a cap on the maximum number of CO₂ emission allowances for the included sectors. The EU reviewed and amended its regulation with a new ambitious target to reduce emissions from the existing EU ETS sectors and maritime by 62% by 2030, compared to 2005 levels. The revised EU ETS Directive also introduces a carbon pricing to fuel combustion in road transport and buildings and additional sectors (ETS2). It is planned to price emissions from 2027/2028 without free allocation to contribute to 42% emission reductions by 2030 compared to 2005 in the covered sectors (Spain and European Commission, 2023).

In the revised Effort Sharing Regulation, the EU legislation sets individual binding reduction targets for Member States for GHG emissions not covered by the existing EU ETS, such as domestic transport (except aviation), buildings, agriculture, waste and small industries with an EU-level GHG emissions reduction target of 40% by 2030 compared to 2005. In the LULUCF sector, the EU adopted a Union net GHG removals target of 310 million tons of CO₂ eq., as a sum of the reported GHG net emissions and removals in the sector in 2030. Additionally, the new legislation includes all emissions and removals reported for all managed in the EU land.

Among additional financial instruments are:

- Social Climate Fund to support vulnerable households, micro-enterprises and transport users. A maximum amount of 65 billion EUR will be available for the period 2026-2032.
- EU ETS-funded Modernisation Fund to contribute to the significant investment needs of the 13 lower-income Member States (reported in 2024).
- The Modernisation Fund is funded from revenues from the auctioning of 2% of the total allowances for 2021-30 under the EU ETS and additional allowances transferred by beneficiary Member States. An additional 2.5% of the total allowances in 2024-2030 will be auctioned for the fund.

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- In addition, the EU ETS's Innovation Fund is one of the world's largest funding programmes for the demonstration of innovative low-carbon technologies. The Innovation Fund, funded 100% by the EU ETS, will support about 38 billion EUR in 2020 -2030 (at carbon price 75 EUR/tCO₂), for the commercial demonstration of innovative low-carbon technologies, to decarbonise Europe and support its transition to climate neutrality.
- A carbon border adjustment mechanism (CBAM) will put a price on the CO₂ content of imported selection of products.
- The primary objective of CBAM is to prevent carbon leakage and increase in CO₂ emissions in third countries and to be sure that imported products will bear the same CO₂ price as EU domestic producers. It will be applied according to international trade rules, and its application will support the deeper international cooperation.

As an update of the EU and its Member States Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC), the EU and its Member States are committed to reduce the net GHGE by at least 55% compared to 1990 by 2030. In the Annex "Information to facilitate clarity, transparency and understanding of the updated nationally determined contribution of the European Union and its Member States for the timeframe 2021-2030" the following numbers of emission reduction plans are provided:

- Under Directive (EU) 2023/959 the EU ETS: the EU will reduce its emissions from the sectors included in this legislation by 62% by 2030 compared to 2005.
 - Regulation (EU) 2023/857 sets an EU-level to decrease 40% of GHGE by 2030, compared to 2005, for the sectors that it covers.
 - Under the Regulation (EU) 2023/857 Greece and Italy will reduce their emissions from 2005 levels by 2030 by the following percentage: Greece 22.7%, Italy 43.7%.
1. Regulation (EU) 2023/839 (which amends Regulation (EU) 218/841) sets a Union binding target of net removals in the LULUCF sector. The geographical scope of the target is now the complete area covered by managed land in the EU. Each Member State has a binding national target for 2030 for the increase of net GHG removals, which together will deliver the collective EU target of 310 Mt CO₂ net removals. In addition, each Member State commits to achieve a sum of net GHGE and removals for 2026-2029.
 - Under Regulation (EU) 2023/839 the target for 2030 for Greece and Italy (as for each MS) is an increase in net removals compared to data from 2016 to 2018 reported in 2032, as follows: Greece -1154 Kt CO₂ eq., Italy -3158 Kt CO₂ eq.

Some additional important citations from the Annex, answering the question on "How the Party considers that its nationally determined contribution is fair and ambitious in the light of its national circumstances":

- The EU has a long experience in climate policies delivering. Its total GHG emissions (excluding LULUCF and international aviation) decreased by 1939 million tonnes CO₂ eq. since 1990 (or 34,3%) reaching its lowest level in 2020 (3708 million tonnes CO₂ eq.). The EU has decoupled its gross domestic product (GDP) from its GHG emissions compared to 1990, with an increase in GDP by 54% and decrease of about 34% of emissions during the same period.
- According to the IPCC 6th Assessment Report, global GHGE need to fall by about 43% below 2019 levels by 2030 to limit warming to 1.5°C. The EU's "at least -55%" target is consistent with this level of reduction, based on the significant emissions reductions recorded by the EU since the base year 1990.
- EU has already reduced greenhouse emissions to 31% below 1990 levels, while at the same time emissions have risen by over 50% worldwide. The EU has significantly exceeded its 2020 targets, without accounting the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic. During 1990-2020 the EU and its Member States' emissions reductions outpaced those of any other major developed or developing economy.
- On a per capita basis, EU emissions are also among the lowest of any major high-income economy and lower than several emerging economies.

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3 MULTILATERAL ENVIRONMENTAL AGREEMENTS

At the international level, the most important regulations affecting CCS are the international conventions dealing with the transboundary shipments of CO₂. These include the *Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment and the Coastal Region of the Mediterranean* (Barcelona Convention), the Protocol to the *Convention on the Prevention of Marine Pollution by Dumping of Wastes and Other Matter* (London Protocol) and the Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic (known as the *OSPAR Convention*). Italy and Greece are among the 21 Parties to the Barcelona Convention and members of the London Convention, however, only Italy has also ratified the London Protocol.

3.1 LONDON CONVENTION AND LONDON PROTOCOL

3.1.1 LONDON CONVENTION

The London Convention, adopted in 1972, is an international agreement on the disposal of waste at sea. It was one of the first international conventions on the protection of the marine environment and has been administered by the International Maritime Organisation since 1977. The Convention prohibits the dumping of certain hazardous materials and requires a special permit for others. It defines 'dumping' as the deliberate disposal of waste from ships, aircraft, platforms, or other man-made structures. Amendments in 1993 banned the dumping of low-level radioactive waste at sea and phased out the dumping of industrial waste by December 1995. There are currently 87 States Parties to the 1972 London Convention (IMO, 2023a, Fig.1).

3.1.2 LONDON PROTOCOL

In 1996, Parties of the London Convention adopted a "*Protocol to the Convention on the Prevention of Marine Pollution by Dumping of Wastes and Other Matter of 1972*", known as the London Protocol (LP). The LP entered into force in 2006. The LP is a separate treaty from the Convention and may be ratified by States that are not part of the Convention.

The LP is the more modern and comprehensive of the two global treaties relating on the prevention of marine pollution by dumping at sea. It provides the precautionary framework needed for parties to effectively prevent pollution of the sea caused by dumping of waste and other matter, incineration, and new activities such as marine geoengineering or carbon capture and storage. Nowadays, the LP is one of the key pillars of marine environmental protection within the international regulatory framework together with MARPOL, UNCLOS and Regional Seas Agreements.

In December 2023 the London Protocol 1996 counts 54 Parties, and 87 parties are members of the London Convention 1972 (Figure 1, IMO, 2023a). The Protocol, which is meant to eventually replace the 1972 Convention, represents a major change of approach to the question of how to regulate the use of the sea as a depository for waste materials. Rather than stating which materials may not be dumped, it prohibits all dumping, except for possibly acceptable wastes on the so-called "reverse list", included in an annex to the Protocol.

As for the two regions investigated in this report: Greece is a party to the London Convention of 1972 but has not ratified the London Protocol 1996, meanwhile, Italy is party of both, the LC and LP (IMO, 2023a).

The London Protocol stresses the "*precautionary approach*", which requires that "*appropriate preventative measures are taken when there is reason to believe that wastes or other matter introduced into the marine environment are likely to cause harm even when there is no conclusive*

evidence to prove a causal relation between inputs and their effects"¹. It also emphasises that the principle that "the polluter should, in principle, bear the cost of pollution" should not be seen as a mere transfer of pollution costs¹". The effects of rising CO₂ levels on the marine environment and the control of new climate engineering technologies are also addressed by the London Convention and Protocol. These advanced international regulatory instruments focus on carbon capture and storage (CCUS) in subsea geological formations and marine climate engineering, such as ocean fertilisation. The 1996 Protocol restricts all dumping actions except for these considered as permitted and listed in Annex 1 (which still requires permits). In 2007 the amendment entered into force and the Protocol Parties adopted a "Specific guidelines for Assessment of Carbon Dioxide Streams for Disposal into Sub-seabed Geological Formations".

Article 4 of the LP states that LP Parties "shall prohibit the dumping of any wastes or other matter except those listed in Annex 1". The CO₂ streams from CO₂ capture processes are in the list of permitted substances. The amendments state that CO₂ disposal is permitted only into a sub-seabed geological formation, carbon dioxide streams should consist overwhelmingly of carbon dioxide (they may contain incidental associated substances derived from the source material and the capture and sequestration processes used), and no wastes or other matter are added to dispose the CO₂ streams.

3.1.2.1 AMENDMENT TO ARTICLE 6

An amendment was adopted in 2009 to address the potential incompatibility between Article 6 of the LP and CCS activities. The former Article 6, in fact, prohibits the "export of wastes or other matter to other countries for dumping or incineration at sea", while the 2009 amendments Article 6 (LP.3(4)) enabling - exclusively - the export of carbon dioxide streams for sequestration in transboundary sub-seabed geological formations. However, this amendment has not yet entered into force as only 10 countries have adopted it by December 2023. By December 2023 it was accepted only by 10 countries: Norway and the UK in 2011, The Netherlands in 2014, Iran in 2016, Finland in 2017, Estonia in 2019, Sweden in 2020, Denmark, Belgium and the Republic of Korea in 2022 (IMO, 2023b). However, the amendment to the LP requires acceptance by two-thirds of the Parties to enter into force. **Italy** is a London Protocol party but has not yet accepted the amendment to Article 6 of the LP. **Greece** is a London Convention party, but not a party of the LP.

3.1.2.2 PROVISIONAL APPLICATION OF THE 2009 AMENDMENT TO ARTICLE 6 OF THE LP

The fourteenth Meeting of the Contracting Parties to the Protocol, decided on October 11, 2019, to allow for the provisional application of the 2009 amendment pending its entry into force by those Contracting Parties which have deposited a declaration to this effect.

Until now only seven countries sent declarations to the Secretary-General of IMO on their provisional applications of the 2009 amendment, pending entry into force. Among these countries, Norway and The Netherlands sent their declarations in 2020, while Denmark, Republic of Korea, UK, Belgium and Sweden sent their declarations to IMO in 2022 (IMO, 2023b). It appears that **Italy** has the intention of depositing a formal declaration of provisional application of the 2009 amendment to Article 6 of the LP and to enter discussions with France and Greece to conclude bilateral agreements on transboundary transport of CO₂ to develop projects for permanent geological storage under the seabed.

¹ London Protocol, Article 3 (<https://www.epa.gov/sites/default/files/2015-10/documents/lpamended2006.pdf>)

Fig.1 _ Parties of London Convention 1972 and London Protocol 1996 (IMO, 2023 a)

3.2 OSPAR CONVENTION

Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic (OSPAR Convention, 1992) includes 15 Countries of the western coasts and catchments of Europe, and the EU, cooperating to protect the marine environment of the NE Atlantic (Figs. 2, 3). OSPAR Convention was started with the Oslo Convention against dumping in 1972. It was extended in 1974 to include land-based sources and the offshore industry by the Paris Convention. The two conventions were unified, updated and broadened by the 1992 OSPAR Convention. The new annex on biodiversity and ecosystems was adopted in 1998 to cover non-polluting human activities that can adversely affect the sea (OSPAR COMMISSION, 2018). The OSPAR Convention text was amended in 1998, and updated in 2002, 2005 and 2006. Amendments to Annexes II and III were adopted at OSPAR 2007.

Under the Rules of Procedure, the OSPAR Commission consists of representatives of each of its 16 Contracting Parties. The Contracting Parties are Belgium, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Iceland, Ireland, Luxembourg, The Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland and the United Kingdom, together with the EU.

Annex II on the prevention and elimination of pollution by dumping or incineration includes Article 1, stating that it should not apply to any deliberate disposal in the maritime area of (a) wastes or other matter from offshore installations; (b) offshore installations and offshore pipelines; Article 2 (Incineration is prohibited) and Article 3:

•The dumping of all wastes or other matter is prohibited, except for the wastes or other matter included in paragraphs 2 and 3 of the Article 3. This list includes the following:

CO₂ streams from CO₂ capture processes for storage, provided that:

- o disposal is into a sub-soil geological formation
- o the streams consist only of CO₂ (carbon dioxide) and may include incidental associated substances from the source material and the capture, transport and storage processes used
- o no wastes or other matter are added for disposal
- o they are intended to permanently stay in these formations and will not cause the significant adverse consequences for the marine environment, human health and other legitimate uses of the marine area.

Fig. 2 _ Parties of OSPAR Convention
■ Signatory states
■ European Union

Fig. 3 _ OSPAR maritime area – the Arctic (I), the Greater North Sea (II), the Celtic Seas, the Bay of Biscay/Golfe de Gascogne (III) and Iberian waters (IV), and the Wider Atlantic (V) www.ospar.org

3.3 BARCELONA CONVENTION

Barcelona Convention (BC) – is the Convention for the Protection of the Mediterranean Sea Against Pollution. It was adopted on 16 February 1976 in Barcelona, entered into force in 1978, and was amended in 1995, when it was renamed to the Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment and the Coastal Region of the Mediterranean. The amendments to the BC entered into force in 2004. The BC and its seven Protocols adopted in the framework of the Mediterranean Action Plan (MAP) constitute the principal regional legally binding Multilateral Environmental Agreement (MEA) in the Mediterranean UNEP/MAP and the Contracting Parties to the BC – 21 Mediterranean countries and the EU (Fig. 4). The amendments adopted in 1995 have yet to be ratified by Bosnia and Herzegovina (UNEP/MAP, 2024a).

3.3.1 DUMPING PROTOCOL

The Protocol for the Prevention of Pollution of the Mediterranean Sea by Dumping from Ships and Aircraft (Dumping Protocol) was entered into force in 1978. Its objective is to take measures to prevent, abate and fully eliminate possible pollution of the Mediterranean Sea by dumping of wastes or other matter.

In 1995, the Dumping Protocol was amended and renamed to Protocol for the Prevention and Elimination of Pollution of the Mediterranean Sea by Dumping from Ships and Aircraft or Incineration at the Sea. The amendments to the Dumping Protocol did not yet enter into the force; it prohibits all dumping activities excluding wastes or other matters listed in the Protocol, including dredged material, fish wastes, vessels (until 31 December 2000), platforms, and inert, uncontaminated geological material. The Mediterranean Pollution Assessment and Control Programme (MED POL) helps Contracting Parties to meet their obligations under the Dumping Protocol (UNEP/MAP, 2024b).

The Dumping Protocol from 1995 is more like the London Protocol and is, therefore, more restrictive, and precautionary. As with the LP, the 1995 Dumping Protocol departs from its predecessor's black-and grey-list approach in favour of the reverse list. Only the waste or other matter listed in Article 4(2) may be considered for dumping acting as an exception to the general ban introduced in Article 4(1). Here, one encounters the same issue as the LP and OSPAR Convention did before it – CO₂ is not listed as an exception and can therefore not be stored as the definition of dumping includes storage activities. The implications are that the 1976 Protocol still applies and one may be able to store CO₂

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with a general permit under this interpretation. If the 1995 Protocol enters into force unamended, storage of CO₂ would be prohibited. CO₂ would likely have to be added to the list of exceptions in Article 4 to allow for this activity, as was the case with the OSPAR Convention and LP before it (Honegger et al, 2023).

Italy and Greece are the Contracting Parties to the Barcelona Convention.

Fig. 4 _ The Barcelona Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment and the Coastal Region of the Mediterranean (1995). Map showing the parties to the Convention. Source: (WIKIPEDIA, 2023)

4 EUROPEAN REGULATIONS

4.1 EU CCS DIRECTIVE

Directive 2009/31/EC of the European Parliament and the Council on the geological storage of carbon dioxide (so-called Carbon Capture and Storage Directive – hereinafter ‘CCS Directive’) establishes a legal framework for the environmentally safe geological storage of CO₂. The aim of the CCS Directive is to be sure that there is no significant risk of leakage of CO₂ or damage to health or the environment, and to prevent any adverse effects on the security of the transport network or storage sites (European Commission, 2009).

4.1.1 IMPLEMENTATION OF EU CCS DIRECTIVE

Public authorities of the studied EU countries responsible for the implementation of the EU CCS Directive reported to the EC about results from the CCS Directive transposition every 3 years (2013, 2016, 2019 and 2023) (European Commission, 2023b).

Italy. To implement Directive 2009/31/EC, Italy passed a new legislation to regulate the geological storage of carbon dioxide. Legislative Decree No 162 of 14 September 2011 entered into force on 5 October 2011 (Decreto Legislativo. n. 162, 2011). CO₂ storage is permitted in Italy both onshore and offshore except for the seismic areas. Exploration and storage permits are always required (Table 3).

Italy did not submit its report about the CCS Directive to the EC in 2023. However, in December 2023, it published a Legislative Decree n.181, namely “Urgent provisions for the country’s energy security,

the promotion of the use of renewable energy sources, support for energy-intensive businesses and for reconstruction in the territories affected by the exceptional flood events that occurred starting from 1 May 2023” (GU General Series n.287 of 09-12-2023) which entered into force on 10/12/2023 (Decreto Legge, 2023). The part 7 of this decree, amended the Legislative Decree No 162 of 14 September 2011, which previously regulated the CO₂ storage in suitable geological formation. The amendments shall apply to requests for obtaining exploration licences, applications for authorisation to carry out experimental programmes of geological storage of CO₂ and applications for CO₂ authorisations of CO₂ geological storage submitted after the date of entry into force of this Decree. The amendments are made to number of the Articles of the Legislative Decree No 162. More precisely, the Legislative Decree No 181 defines experimental programmes for the geological storage of CO₂ as “a geological storage of CO₂ that takes place, over a period limited and for experimental purposes, in deposits of spent hydrocarbons located in the territorial sea and within the exclusive economic zone and the continental shelf”, while authorisations for the carrying out experimental programmes for the geological storage of CO₂ shall be issued to applicants, on the advice of the Committee, by the Ministry of Environment and Energy Security. During the period of validity of the authorisation, no incompatible uses of the site under investigation are allowed by the provisions of the authorisation itself. Finally, regulations were added „for the case of more than one storage site in the same hydraulic unit the potential pressure interactions must be such that all sites simultaneously comply with the provisions of this Decree” (Decreto Legge, 2023).

Greece. In Greece, the Ministerial Decision 48416/2037/E.103/2011 (Government Gazette B’ 2516, 2011), as amended, transposed the CCS Directive 2009/31/EC into Greek law. The decision largely follows the principles of the EU CCS Directive. Industrial CO₂ storage is permitted both onshore and offshore, except for areas where the storage complex extends beyond Greek territory. Exploration and storage permits are always required (Table 3).

The recent law L.4920/2022 (art.228 par.1), as amended by L.4964/2022 (Article 175), designates the Hellenic Hydrocarbons and Energy Resources Management Company (HEREMA) as the competent authority for the licensing, monitoring and supervision of carbon dioxide storage projects. Moreover, Article 173 of L.4964/2022 introduces a new licensing process for CO₂ exploration and storage permits for economical operators who already hold hydrocarbon exploration and production rights in areas which could potentially be used for carbon dioxide storage (HEREMA, 2023).

Table 3. National CCS laws (Decreto Legislativo n. 162, 2011, Government Gazette B’ 2516, 2011)

Country	Industrial CO ₂ Storage permitted		Exploration and storage permits are always required
	Onshore	Offshore	
Italy	Except for seismic areas	Except for seismic areas	Yes
Greece	Except for areas where the storage complex extends beyond Greek territory	Except areas where the storage complex extends beyond Greek territory	Yes

4.1.2 AMENDMENT OF EXISTING EU DIRECTIVES

The CCS Directive has amended six existing EU Directives to protect the environment and human health from the risks connected to the geological storage of CO₂. All EU Member States communicated

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with the EC for their transposing measures and made amendments to four of their existing instruments regulated by the:

- (1) EIA (Environmental Impact Assessment) Directive,
- (2) Waste Framework Directive,
- (3) Industrial Emission Directive and
- (4) Large Combustion Plant Directive.

Member States which allow CO₂ storage in their countries also amended laws regulated by

- (5) Water Framework Directive and
- (6) Environmental Liability Directive (Articles 31-35 and 37; European Commission, 2009).

As a result:

- capture and transport of CO₂ stream is covered by national instruments regulated by (1) and (3),
- CO₂ captured and transported for geological storage is excluded from the national waste regulations (2),
- and Operators of combustion plants with a capacity of 300 MW or more should assess conditions and demonstrate that the plant is built "capture-ready" (4) in all the Member States.

CO₂ is allowed for injection into saline reservoirs according to instruments regulated by (5) and operation of CO₂ storage sites is allowed according to amendments made in instruments regulated by (6) in countries permitting CO₂ storage (EC, 2014, Shogenova et. al., 2014).

4.1.3 ASSESSING OF STORAGE CAPACITY AND APPLICATION FOR EXPLORATION AND STORAGE PERMITS

In EU GeoCapacity project CO₂ storage capacity in Italy was estimated in deep saline aquifers as 4669 Mt and in hydrocarbon fields as 1810 Mt (Vangkilde-Pedersen et.al., 2009).

When examining and assessing the storage capacity available on the national territory as well as when granting exploration and temporary storage permits, the competent authorities in Italy must refer to Annex 1 of the Decree, which contains all the technical parameters specified in Annex 1 of the Directive (Decreto Legislativo n. 162, 2011).

Article 8(1) of the Decree stipulates that new surveys and exploration are allowed for the selection of storage sites using a special permit if the information available (from the database referred to in Article 6) is not sufficient.

Nowadays, ENI and SNAM are launching the Ravenna CCS project in Italy, with a total storage capacity of 500 Mt of CO₂ and start-up expected in 2024 (Phase 1) and at the end of 2026 (Phase 2). The captured CO₂ will be stored in the offshore depleted gas fields in the Adriatic Sea.

Although storage capacity has been estimated for the Italian area, a more detailed study is required for estimation since no CCS projects have been implemented yet (Ministry of the Environment and Energy Security of Italy, 2023). Italy has developed a national maritime spatial planning (<https://maritime-spatial-planning.ec.europa.eu/countries/Italy>). However, it does not mention CCUS.

In the EUGeoCapacity project different potential sites for CO₂ storage in Greece with total theoretical storage capacity in deep saline aquifers and hydrocarbon fields of 2190 Mt were reported (Vangkilde-Pedersen et.al., 2009). The total effective storage capacity in aquifers alone in Greece was estimated to be around 184 Mt (Hatziyannis, 2009). This CO₂ storage capacity concerns the Tertiary sedimentary basins of Prinos, West Thessaloniki and a part of the Mesohellenic Trough (Hatziyannis, 2009). CO₂ storage capacity in the Miocene Pentalofos Formation was estimated recently as 1435 Gt CO₂ (Koukouzas and Gemeni, 2019).

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Greece is still in the process of identifying the areas from which storage sites may be selected following Article 4(1) of the EU CCS directive. Although a preliminary assessment of potential storage areas has been conducted, this has only been done on a qualitative basis and no specific areas have been officially designated yet. However, the Prinos Basin, which includes the almost depleted offshore Prinos oil field, is currently a mature candidate site for carbon storage in Greece, for which an exploration permit was issued by HEREMA to Energean in September 2022, following the permitting process of L. 4964/2022 (HEREMA, 2023).

Preliminary studies to determine potential areas for CO₂ storage in Greece have been mainly based on the type of geological formations, the “reservoir” quality of the rocks present, and the proximity to industrial clusters with considerable CO₂ emissions. Three types of areas are considered: saline aquifers, O&G fields and mafic rocks. Social acceptance and concurrent land/marine uses have not yet been addressed. More detailed studies are currently planned to designate in the coming years general areas from which potential storage sites may be selected for exploration.

As of September 2022, only one exploration permit of 22-month duration has been issued in Greece for CO₂ storage. The permit was granted to Energean, according to National Law 4964/2022, to explore the potential for CO₂ storage at the Prinos complex, where it currently holds the oil & gas exploration and production rights. It is anticipated that the potential operator will submit a storage permit application before the end of the second quarter of 2024 (HEREMA, 2023).

4.1.4 MONITORING REQUIREMENTS

Monitoring is one of the key activities required by the CCS Directive to ensure the safety of geological storage. The main requirements in the area are stated in Article 13 (European Commission, 2009), as follows.

“Member States shall ensure that the operator carries out monitoring of the injection facilities, the storage complex (including where possible the CO₂ plume), and where appropriate the surrounding environment for:

- comparison between the actual and modelled behaviour of CO₂ and formation water, in the storage site;
- detecting significant irregularities;
- detecting migration of CO₂;
- detecting leakage of CO₂;
- detecting significant adverse effects on the surrounding environment, including in particular on drinking water, for human population, or users of the surrounding biosphere;
- assessing the effectiveness of any corrective measures taken under Article 16;
- updating the safety and integrity assessment of the storage complex in the short- and long-term, and the assessment that stored CO₂ will be completely and permanently stayed underground.

Monitoring shall be based on a monitoring plan designed by the operator. The plan shall be updated under the requirements of Annex II (European Commission, 2009) every five years to take into account changes in assessed risk of leakage, changes to the assessed risks to the environment and human health, new scientific evidence, and improvements in the best available technology and should be re-submitted to the competent authority for approval (Table 4).

The Italian CCS Decree includes Annex I (analogue to Annex I to CCS directive about characterisation and assessment of the potential storage complex) and Annex II (criteria for establishing and updating the plan) analogue to the Annex II to CCS directive. The monitoring programme must be updated every five years in accordance with the provisions of this Description. According to Article 10 of the Law, the operator is requested to monitor the CO₂ injection facilities, the storage complex, and the CO₂ accumulation and environment, where necessary. Chapter VI and Chapter VII of the Description outline the procedures and provisions for the ‘Reporting Requirements for Operators’ and for the ‘Supervision of CO₂ Geological Storage Activity’, respectively. Both statements comply with the

provisions set out in Article 14 of the CCS Directive for Reporting and Article 15 of the Directive for Inspections (Decreto Legislativo n. 162, 2011).

On the other hands, CCS monitoring regulations in Greece are very much in line with EU CCS Directive (Government Gazette B' 2516, 2011).

In addition to the CCS Directive, monitoring should also address the requirements under the European Union Emission Trading Scheme (EU ETS) and its Monitoring and Reporting Guidelines (MRG). The MRG are set out in relevant documents such as: Commission Decision 2007/589/EC on MRG; Commission Decision 2010/345/EU amending Commission Decision 2007/589/EC. In addition to the CCS Directive's requirement to detect leakage, the provisions under the EU ETS require that any leaked emissions that occur from storage activities are quantified and reported to determine the allowances that must be surrendered under the EU ETS and to monitor the effectiveness of CO₂ storage as a GHG mitigation technology.

Table 4. EU and National Requirements for CO₂ Storage Site Monitoring

	During Storage			Post-closure period			Operator obligations
	Reporting to competent authority	Monitoring plan updating	Competent authority Routine inspections	Routine inspections by competent authority	After transfer of responsibility	Operator obligations	
				3 years after closure	Until transfer of responsibility (minimum 20 years)	Routine inspections	Financial contribution to monitoring costs
EU CCS Directive	At least once a year	Every 5 years	At least once a year	At least once a year	Every 5 years	May be reduced or intensified in case of problem	30 years
Italy, CCS regulations	By 31 March of each year. Within 30 days in case of permit withdrawal	Every 5 years	At least once a year	At least once a year	At least every 5 years	May be reduced or intensified in case of problem	30 years
Greece, CCS regulations	At least once a year	Every 5 years	At least once a year	At least once a year	Every 5 years	May be reduced or intensified in case of problem	30 years

4.1.5 THIRD-PARTY ACCESS TO TRANSPORT NETWORK AND STORAGE SITE AND TRANSBOUNDARY ISSUES

Article 21 of CCS directive encourages Member States to take the measures enabling potential users to obtain access to transport networks and storage sites for the purpose of geological storage of captured CO₂. According to the CCS directive operators of transport networks and of storage sites

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“may refuse access on the grounds of lack of capacity. Duly substantiated reasons shall be given for any refusal.”

Article 24 of CCS Directive encourages transboundary cooperation for cases of cross-border transport of CO₂, cross-border storage site or cross-border storage complexes. For such cooperation competent authorities of the Member States shall jointly meet the requirements of the CCS Directive and other relevant EU legislations. The CCS directive encourages bilateral agreements between countries to arrange for transboundary CO₂ transport to circumvent the London Protocol prohibiting the export of CO₂ as waste (European Commission, 2009).

Italian CCS Decree in Article 28 obliges operators of CO₂ transport networks and storage sites to guarantee the connection and free access to its transportation network and storage sites to other operators in the transparent and non-discriminatory manner. However, it is also stated that “transport network operators and operators of storage sites may refuse access for lack of ability or link”. Transnational cooperation is regulated only in short by Article 30 of Italian CCS Decree: “For cross-border transport of CO₂ storage sites or transboundary storage complexes, the Ministry of economic development and the Ministry of environment shall fulfil the provisions of this Decree and other applicable Community standards or promote the conclusion of agreements with countries outside the European Union”.

According to the Italian draft NECP 2023, „to allow for cross-border projects, Italy intends to deposit a formal declaration of provisional application of the 2009 amendment to Article 6 of the London Protocol and to enter discussions with France and Greece to conclude bilateral agreements on transboundary transport of CO₂ to develop projects for CO₂ geological storage under the seabed” (Ministry of the Environment and Energy Security of Italy, 2023).

The Greek CCS Regulation describes access to the transmission system and storage sites in the article 22 (Government Gazette B' 2516, 2011). Potential users can get access to CO₂ transport networks and storage sites for geological storage of produced and captured CO₂ in accordance with paragraphs 2, 3 and 4. 2. The Competent Authority (which is now HEREMA) shall take all necessary legislative and administrative measures to ensure that such access is provided in a transparent and non-discriminatory manner. For fair and open access, the above service shall consider:

- (a) the storage capacity available within the areas designated pursuant to Article 5, and the transport capacity available or reasonably available;
- (b) the percentage of the country's CO₂ reduction obligations under international conventions and agreements and Community legislation;
- (c) the need to refuse access where there is an incompatibility of technical specifications which cannot easily be overcome;
- (d) the need to meet the duly substantiated reasonable needs of the owner or operator of the storage site or transport network and the interests of all other users of the storage site or transport network or handling units that may be affected.

Transmission system operators and storage site operators may refuse access based on lack of capacity. This refusal must be adequately justified and notified to the competent authority. An operator refusing access based on lack of capacity or connection shall make the necessary improvements if it is economically advantageous. In any case, the operator is obliged to inform the competent authority (Government Gazette B' 2516, 2011).

In 2023 Greece reported to the EC: „There is no experience with transboundary CO₂ transport and there are currently no plans for transboundary CO₂ storage sites or complexes. However, the planned Prinos CO₂ storage project is expected to be the only available storage solution for regional emitters in hard-to-abate sectors. Provided that its suitability for carbon storage is confirmed, it is expected

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that it could receive CO₂ from other EU emitters outside Greece via ships (e.g., from Italy)". (HEREMA, 2023).

In its NECP 2023 Italy reported that together with France and Greece, a regional plan to support the development of CCS infrastructure in the Mediterranean Sea basin within the scope of the TEN-E Regulation was developed and presented in March 2023 (Italian Ministry of the Environment and Energy Security, 2023).

The cross-border plan is scalable, and the development of CCS value chains allows the promotion of further projects in the region. As a result, other Mediterranean countries could join later to strengthen regional cooperation on CCS.

By engaging in enhanced collaboration, France, Greece, and Italy have expressed a common interest in facilitating CCS projects: maximising synergies on the processes of liquefaction, transport and storage of CO₂ and promoting third-party access infrastructure are key factors for the uptake of CO₂ capture in EU Member States intending to use CO₂ capture.

The Mediterranean CCS Plan provides a framework for discussions and cooperation between its signatories but does not impose any legal, regulatory, or political constraints and does not replace national CCS policies and strategies.

The development of a CCUS (Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage) hub, where many CO₂ emitters can benefit from common infrastructure and an open access cross-border transport network, is crucial because not all Member States have access to adequate geological storage sites. The value chains of liquefaction, transport and storage of CO₂ will need to be developed at a regional level.

4.2 EU ETS

The EU ETS phase 1 started in 2005 to 2007 as a pilot phase, and phase 2 (2008-2012) is corresponded to the first commitment period of the Kyoto Protocol. Since January 2012 aviation was included. Since phase 3 (2013-2020) more sectors and gases were included, a single EU-wide cap was included auctioning was applied to distributing allowances, and the rules for free allocation were harmonised. By 2020, emissions covered by the EU ETS decreased by 41% compared to 2005, that is about two times higher than the 2020 target of a 21% reduction under phase 3.

EU ETS phase 4 (2021-2030) had a cap which was aligned with the previous 2030 target to reduce EU GHG emissions by 40%, compared to 1990 levels.

The legislative proposal in the 'Fit for 55' package to review the ETS aims to align the emissions trading in phase 4 with the new 2030 target included in the European Climate Law to reduce net GHGE by 55%, by lowering the cap, including more sectors and improving the functioning of the EU ETS.

As part of the 'Fit for 55' package, the EC published a legislative proposal for a revision of the EU ETS in July 2021, to align it with the new target of a 55% reduction of EU net GHGE by 2030, compared to 1990 levels. In addition, the Effort-Sharing Regulation (ESR EU) 2018/842 and the Land Use, Land-use Change and Forestry Regulation (EU) 2018/841 and other energy and climate legislation were reviewed.

The EU ETS launched in 2005 covers about 45% of EU greenhouse gas emissions.

The EC proposal to amend Directive 2003/87/EC concerns the ongoing phase 4 of the ETS (2021-2030). It consists of five main elements:

- a reduced cap and more ambitious linear reduction factor for GHG emissions,
- revised rules for free allocation of allowances and the market stability reserve,
- extension of the ETS to maritime transport,
- a separate new ETS for buildings and road transport,
- increase of the Innovation and Modernisation Funds and new rules on the use of ETS revenues.

To align the EU ETS Directive with the increased GHG emission reduction targets set in the European Climate Law, the Commission proposed to reduce the emissions from the EU ETS sectors (including the extension to the maritime sector) by 61% by 2030, compared to 2005 levels. To achieve this target, the proposal increases the linear emissions reduction factor from 2.2% per year to 4.2%.

The EU ETS will cover CO₂ emissions from large maritime transport, (ships above 5,000 gross tonnages). The requirement to surrender allowances would be gradually phased out in 2023-2025.

The Council and European Parliament agreed to further increase the emission reduction target by 2030 in EU ETS sectors to minus 62 % compared to 2005 levels. More specific suggestions to improve MRV on issues such as on the transfer of CO₂ have been made. The introduction of a separate emissions trading scheme for buildings and road transport will also have an impact on the design of MRV processes and verifier capacity (European Commission, 2023 c).

Decision (EU) 2015/1814 establishing the ETS market stability reserve (MSR) would be amended to enable a smoother intake of allowances to the reserve. From 2023, allowances above the level of auction volumes of the previous year would be invalidated, and the number of allowances in the MSR would be limited to 400 million.

On 18 May 2022, as part of the REPowerEU initiative, the Commission presented a legislative proposal that amends the EU ETS Directive and the MSR decision to auction €20 billion worth of allowances from the market stability reserve. The auction revenue would be made available to the Recovery and Resilience Facility.

The European Economic and Social Committee adopted an opinion on the proposal on 8 December 2021. The European Committee of the Regions adopted an opinion entitled 'Making ETS and CBAM work for EU cities and regions' on 28 April 2022.

In the European Parliament, the proposal has been referred to the Committee on Environment, Public Health and Food Safety (ENVI) and it was adopted in June 2022. The adopted text aims to reduce GHG emissions in the ETS sectors by 63% by 2030 and introduces a bonus-malus system to incentivise best performers and innovation. It aims to raise the ambition of the maritime transport sector and establish an Ocean Fund to support maritime decarbonisation. Free allowances in sectors covered by the CBAM should be phased out between 2027 and 2032. The adopted text sets the starting date for the ETS II to 2024 for commercial buildings and road transport, while residential buildings and private road transport would be included from 2029.

Table 5. CO₂ Emissions from industrial installations as a percentage of the previous year (EU ETS, 2024)

Country	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Italy	92.87	102.24	99.27	100.2	94.47	96.3	87.72
Greece	94.66	90.45	93.13	107.01	95.28	86.4	77.26

4.2.1 MONITORING AND REPORTING GUIDELINES

The Monitoring and Reporting Guidelines (MRG) under the EU ETS Directive (Commission Decision 2007/589/EC and its amendment Commission Decision 2010/345/EU) provide monitoring and reporting guidelines for GHGE from the capture, transport and geological storage of CO₂. The MRG specifies how emissions of the CO₂ storage activity must be accounted for and reported for purposes of the EU ETS (MRG Annexes I (e.g. Section 4.3) and XVIII). The following emission sources at a storage site must be monitored under the EU ETS:

- Combustion emissions at the injection site.
- Fugitive emissions and emissions from venting at the injection site.
- Emissions from vents and flaring at enhanced hydrocarbon recovery.
- Leakage from the storage reservoir into the water column or atmosphere.

The MRG emphasizes on the verification, accounting, and reporting of any emissions (i.e., quantification), the relevant content of which is given below. In the MRG one of the guiding principles is to minimize the uncertainty in the quantification of emissions.

4.2.2 INTEGRATION OF EU ETS AND EU CCS DIRECTIVE

Some monitoring methods used for monitoring under the CCS Directive may be suitable for quantification of any emissions resulting from leakage. Furthermore, quantification of any leakage will be useful in assessing the significance of the leakage risk as required under the CCS Directive. Monitoring activities and plans need to meet the requirements of the CCS Directive and should be extended to meet the requirements of the MRG under the EU ETS. It will be more efficient for both the operator and the competent authority of a storage site to set up and manage monitoring on an integrated basis, covering both CCS and EU ETS issues. Emissions sources at the injection site and from enhanced hydrocarbon recovery can be monitored using existing approaches from the MRG. Combustion emissions at injection can be monitored with approaches from Annex II (stationary combustion), vented emissions at injection and enhanced hydrocarbon recovery with approaches from Annex XII (continuous emission measurement) and fugitive emissions at injection by industry best practice. The MRG formats for monitoring plans already exist at the Member State level. This includes industry best practice approaches.

5 NATIONAL CASE STUDIES

5.1 ITALY

5.1.1 GHG AND CO₂ EMISSIONS

Fig. 5 _ GHG emissions in Italy in 1990-2022 (Crippa et al, 2023)

Italy is one of the largest CO₂ emitters in the EU. In 2022 Italy produced 322.95 Mt CO₂ (Table 1) and was in fourth place among the EU27 countries which are the largest CO₂ emitters in EU27. In Italy, CO₂ emissions per capita (5.48 t) were lower than the EU27 average (6.32 t) but higher than the Global Total average (4.84 t) (Table 2).

This could be explained by the large population of Italy (58.937 M) and the leading position in EU27 in using geothermal and solar energy.

In Italy, CO₂ emissions decreased significantly from 1990 to 2022 in all sectors except for transport (-2%) and emissions increased in agriculture from 2005 to 2022 (+3%) (Fig. 5).

Among the largest CO₂ producers were refineries, power plants, the iron and steel industry, cement plants, the chemical industry and waste-to-energy plants.

5.1.2 CCS IN THE NATIONAL ENERGY AND CLIMATE PLAN 2023

Italy submitted its draft updated integrated national energy and climate plan on 19 July 2023. EC accessed, prepared highlights, and made recommendations on December 2023 (European Commission, 2024).

According to the EC assessment:

- 1) Regarding the reduction of GHGE under the Effort Sharing Regulation (ESR), the plan provides emission projections demonstrating that with the additional policies and measures reported in the draft NECP, Italy is not on track to meet its national greenhouse gas target of -43.7% in 2030 compared to 2005 levels (Fig. 6). According to Italy's projections, they would underachieve the target by 6.7 to 8.7%.
- 2) On CCUS, the plan identifies annual CO₂ emissions that can be annually captured and stored by 2050 but did not provide data by 2030. There is no information EU ETS emitters or from other sources. It is not reported when CO₂ storage capacity would become available. There are no numbers for annual CO₂ injection capacity by 2030. The plans for the cross-border CO₂ transport capacities are reported, but domestic CO₂ transport is not reported.

	2030 value submitted in the draft updated NECP	2030 target under EU legislation	Assessment of 2030 ambition level
GHG emissions in ETS sectors (compared to 2005)	-35% to -37%	-43.7%*	Italy does not reach its target based on projections.
GHG net removals in LULUCF (Mt CO ₂ eq. net GHG removals)	-34.9	-3.158 (additional removal target) -35.758 (total net removals)**	Italy does not reach its target based on projections.
Energy Efficiency (Final energy consumption)	94.4 Mtoe	92.1 Mtoe***	Italy's final energy consumption is above the indicated target resulting from EU legislation
Renewable Energy (Share of renewable energy in gross final consumption)	40.5%	39%****	Italy's contribution to the EU target is slightly above the one resulting from EU legislation.

* under the Effort Sharing Regulation (ESR).
 ** under the Regulation on Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF).
 *** according to the formula set out in Annex I of the Directive (EU) 2023/1791 on energy efficiency and amending Regulation (EU) 2023/955 ('EED recast').
 **** according to the formula set out in Annex II of the Regulation (EU) 2018/1999 on the Governance Regulation of the Energy Union and Climate Action.

Fig. 6 _ Italy's key objectives and contributions (European Commission, 2024)

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The EC's recommendations regarding CCUS aim at having an overview of the intended deployment of these technologies at national level, including planned annual volumes of CO₂ to be captured by 2030, reported by source of CO₂ captured from installations covered by Directive 2003/87/EC or from other sources, such as biogenic sources or direct air capture; about planned CO₂ transport infrastructure; and about potential domestic CO₂ storage capacity and injection volumes of CO₂ planned by 2030. EC concluded that Italy should consider EC recommendations when submitting updated NECP by June 30, 2024.

However, Italy's main positive elements and areas of improvement were also highlighted.

CCUS in Italian NECP:

- 1) "To limit emissions, particularly in the industrial sector, the use of CO₂ capture, transport and storage/utilisation (CCUS) will be necessary. For this aim, specific targets for CO₂ capture and storage will be established based on the geological parameters of the relevant storage sites that will be operationally available by 2030 and beyond" (page 11). Pages 65-68 of Italian NECP describe CCS in more detail (Ministry of the Environment and Energy Security of Italy, 2023) the Strategic targets which include CCS, namely:
 - Following the EU Governance Regulation and to ensure consistency between its long-term strategy and the Integrated National Energy and Climate Plan (INECP), Italy published in January 2021 the Italian Long-Term Strategy for the reduction of GHGE, where possible pathways to achieve climate neutrality in Italy by 2050 are described.
 - CCS has been identified as one of the four key levers to be integrated with energy efficiency.
 - CCS is considered as an option to address both combustion and process emissions.
 - The strategy estimated that in Italy 20-40 Mt of CO₂ could be reduced to zero by 2050 using CCS.
 - 418 Mt of CO₂ eq. were produced in Italy in 2019, including 84 Mt from the industrial sector. Of these, 54 Mt (13% of the national total) came from hard-to-abate sectors such as chemicals, cement and steel, for which CCS could be considered as decarbonisation option.

The role and targets of CO₂ capture and storage/use are underlined.

- 1) CCS regulations and their updates are explained as follows:

- a) National:

The CO₂ capture and storage sectors regulated in Europe by Directive 2009/31/EC, transposed in Italy by Legislative Decree No 162/2011, which laid down a legislative framework to allow the storage of CO₂ in appropriate geological formations. It is mentioned "that the regulatory framework is updated to speed up the authorisation process, define the technical rules and requirements for CO₂ transport and storage, and the business model and the associated regulatory framework for CCS". "The INECP 2019 includes the possibility of CO₂ capture and storage in both the energy and industrial sectors by 2040 to achieve full decarbonisation target of the energy system by 2050. CCS facilities were included in the list of infrastructure needed to achieve the INECP objectives (Decree-Law 76/2020 and Decree-Law 77/2021). They are of high public interest and eligible for an accelerated authorisation process. Italy is planning to fill regulatory or procedural gaps in the process of permitting process for CO₂ storage and development of the CCS technology."

- b) International:

To allow for cross-border projects, Italy intends to deposit a formal declaration of provisional application of the 2009 amendment to Article 6 of the London Protocol and to enter discussions with France and Greece to conclude bilateral agreements on transboundary transport of CO₂ to develop projects for CO₂ geological storage under the seabed.

- 2) Storage sites are described as venue where it is technically possible to store CO₂ including depleted deposits (in particular gas fields) and saline aquifers.
- 3) Storage potential: Because of the potential of these fields, an analysis of the storage potential was launched in Italy focusing on depleted oil & gas fields relating only to the ENI mining rights

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portfolio. The results of ENI's analyses showed a storage potential for the oil & gas fields used in Italy of around 750 Mt.

It is mentioned about CO₂ storage capacity in saline aquifers that "assessments from scientific literature have not been verified by operators and should be further developed through dedicated studies complemented by an exploratory phase aimed at assessing the extent of the aquifer and the characterisation of the storage site" (Ministry of the Environment and Energy Security of Italy, 2023).

Given the technical feasibility of storing CO₂ in the various types of deposit described above, Legislative Decree No 76/2020 renewed the legal framework transposing the Directive by introducing special simplification rules. Article 60-bis providing for the suitability of depleted offshore hydrocarbon deposits for use in experimental programmes for the geological storage of CO₂. Therefore, for the application of the current standard for experimental programmes, the CO₂ storage capacity for aquifers is not functional; to date only the CO₂ storage capacity associated with depleted oil & gas fields needs to be considered (Ministry of the Environment and Energy Security of Italy, 2023).

- 4) National projects: To facilitate the start-up of CO₂ storage projects and access to of storage capacity, Italy plans to establish a regulatory framework supporting the rapid deployment of long-term CO₂ geological storage options, the development of CO₂ capture projects and increase in transport infrastructure, including cross-border options. Italy plans to fill regulatory or procedural gaps in the process of permitting storage and development of the CCS industry.
- 5) New objectives of the INECP supported by Italy:
Based on the Italian Long-Term Strategy, the target for reducing GHG emissions is expected to be about 20 - 40 Mt CO₂ by storing CO₂ by 2050, compared with emissions of around 50-60 Mt/year in 2019 from hard-to-abate sectors, for which CCS is a key technology for decarbonisation.
- 6) At the Italian level, the Fund for Sustainable Growth (FCS) is intended to finance programmes that are in line with the objectives of the Green and Innovation Deal and that have as their objective industrial research and experimental development activities, if they are addressed to all companies in general; if they are addressed only to SMEs, support is normally also provided for the industrialisation phase.
- 7) For supporting the development of storage opportunities in Italy, the assessment of CO₂ storage potential including all types of storage sites including depleted deposits and saline aquifers are planned.
- 8) Additionally, the definition of the market/business model and the introduction of support mechanisms for the CCS value chain, in the form of grants supporting capital and operating costs are considered.
- 9) Italy plans to set targets for CCS in the updated INECP, based on the CO₂ geological storage capacity that can be available by 2030 (and later on), starting from the exploitation of depleted offshore hydrocarbon deposits. This storage capacity is more than 500 Mt CO₂ in the offshore depleted gas fields in the Central Adriatic.
- 10) In the planned programmes, a storage capacity of about 100 million tonnes over 25 years in the Ravenna hub storage programme can be made available (Ministry of the Environment and Energy Security of Italy, 2023).

5.1.3 SUMMARY FOR ITALY

Paris Climate Agreement

Italy has ratified the Paris Climate Agreement on 11 Nov 2016.

CO₂ emissions

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Its total fossil CO₂ emissions decreased from 423.3 Mt in 1990 to 322.95 Mt in 2022. CO₂ emissions per capita in Italy decreased from 8.38 t in 2005 (maximum since 1990) to 5.48 tonnes in 2022 (Table 2.2).

Climate and energy strategic targets

Italy planned to reach climate neutrality by 2050. Based on the objectives set by the Italian Lungo Strategy, the target for reducing greenhouse gas emissions is expected to be approximately 20 to 40 Mt CO₂ by 2050 by storing CO₂, compared with emissions of around 50-60 Mt/year in 2019 from hard-to-abate sectors, for which CCS is a key, if not the only, resource for decarbonisation.

Italy defined and submitted to EC its 2030 targets in the National Energy and Climate Plan 2023 (draft), which were estimated by EC as lower than needed and asked to consider EC's recommendation when submitting the final plan in June 2024.

London Protocol

Italy has ratified the London Protocol but has not ratified yet the 2009 amendment to Article 6, enabling the export of carbon dioxide streams for sequestration in transboundary sub-seabed geological formations (Figure 3.1, Table 3.1). Italy intends to deposit a formal declaration of provisional application of the 2009 amendment to Article 6 of the London Protocol and to enter discussions with France and Greece to conclude bilateral agreements on transboundary transport of CO₂ to develop projects for permanent geological storage under the seabed.

OSPAR Convention

Italy is a party of the OSPAR Convention under the European Union sign (Table 3.1).

BARCELONA Convention

Italy is a member of the Barcelona Convention for the Protection of the Mediterranean Sea Against Pollution. Its Protocol, amended in 1995, prohibits all dumping activities with some exceptions, where CO₂ is not yet included. However, the 1995 amendment is not yet in force, and by now CO₂ injection offshore is not prohibited.

EU CCS Directive

Italy passed a new legislation to regulate the geological storage of carbon. Legislative Decree No 162 of 14 September 2011 entered into force on 5 October 2011. CO₂ storage is permitted in Italy except for the seismic areas.

The regulatory framework is being updated, to speed up the authorisation process, to define the technical rules and requirements for the transport and storage of CO₂, as well as the business model and the associated regulatory framework for CCS.

The INECP 2019 recognised the possibility of capturing and storing carbon in both the energy and industrial sectors by 2040 to achieve full decarbonisation of the energy system by 2050. Carbon capture, transport and storage facilities were subsequently explicitly included in the list of infrastructure needed to achieve the INECP objectives (Decree-Law 76/2020 and Decree-Law 77/2021). As such, they are of overriding public interest and eligible for a dedicated accelerated authorisation process. Italy intends to fill any remaining regulatory or procedural gaps in the process of permitting storage and development of the CCS sector.

Prospects for CO₂ storage

Italy has very good geological options for CO₂ storage of CO₂ emissions in depleted gas fields and saline aquifers both onshore and offshore.

CO₂ storage capacity

In the EU GeoCapacity project CO₂ storage capacity in deep saline aquifers was estimated as 4669 Mt and in hydrocarbon fields as 1810 Mt.

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Monitoring requirements of the storage sites in Italian regulations mostly correspond to the EU CCS Directive. Italian CCS Decree includes Annex I (analogue to Annex I to CCS directive about characterisation and assessment of the potential storage complex) and Annex II (criteria for establishing and updating the plan) analogue to the Annex II to CCS directive.

An analysis of the storage potential was launched in Italy focusing on depleted oil & gas fields relating only to the ENI mining rights portfolio. The results of ENI's analyses showed a storage potential for the oil & gas fields used in Italy of around 750 Mt.

Transboundary issues

Italian CCS Decree in Article 28 obliges operators of CO₂ transport networks and storage sites to guarantee the connection and free access to its transportation network and storage sites to other operators in a transparent and non-discriminatory manner. However, it is also stated that "transport network operators and operators of storage sites may refuse access for lack of ability or link". Article 30 of the Italian CCS Decree regulates transnational cooperation on CO₂ storage and requires the Ministry of Economic Development and Environment to comply with the Decree and Community standards while promoting the conclusion of agreements with non-EU countries.

EU ETS Operates in Italy, as an EU Member State.

In 2015 Italy registered in EU ETS 1071 installations, which produced 143635 Kt CO₂. Among them 93 installations produced >0.5 Mt CO₂. CO₂ Emissions from industrial installations as a percentage of the previous year (EU ETS) decreased during 2017-2020, varying from 100.2% in 2017 to 87.72 in 2020.

National CO₂ Tax

Italy has not introduced a national Carbon Tax yet.

50% of Italian policymakers answered "Yes" and 50% answered "Maybe" to the Question about national CO₂ tax in the questionnaire (*If Italy does not have enough financial capacity to support national CCUS clusters and hubs, could a national CO₂ tax be introduced to address this issue?*)

5.2 GREECE

5.2.1 GHG AND CO₂ EMISSIONS

CO₂ emissions decreased from 1990 to 2022 in all sectors of Greece except for transport (+16%) and waste (+6%). In Greece, total fossil CO₂ emissions decreased from 77.9 Mt in 1990 to 56.78 Mt in 2022. CO₂ emissions per capita in Greece decreased from 9.17 t in 2005 (maximum since 1990) to 5.14 t in 2022 (Table 2, Figure 8).

The largest CO₂ producers in Greece are power plants, refineries, and cement plants.

5.2.2 CCS IN THE NATIONAL ENERGY AND CLIMATE PLAN 2023

The European Commission has assessed Greece's draft updated NECP, submitted on 3 November 2023 (Hellenic Republic Ministry of Environment and Energy, 2023). It is reported that "corresponding to the European Climate Law 2021/1119 which established a framework to achieve climate neutrality, Greece adopted for the first time its National Climate Law 4936/2022 (Government Gazette, Series I, No. 105), which includes climatic targets, to reduce GHGE by 55% by 2030 and by 80% by 2040 (compared to 1990 levels), to achieve climate neutrality (i.e. zero total GHGE) by 2050".

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Fig. 7_ GHG emissions in Greece in 1990-2022 (Crippa et al, 2023)

Therefore, "the current NECP incorporates the objectives of the National Climate Law, the objectives of the European Union policy (RE-PowerEU and Fit-for-55 under the Green Deal) and the European directives on renewable energy sources, energy efficiency and others, which are being finalised". In the NECP 2019 Greece planned to reduce GHG emissions by 40% by 2030 compared to 1990. In the revised draft 2023, this number increased to 54 excluding LULUCF CO₂ removals, and the reduction can reach -57% if a higher contribution from LULUCF is achieved by then (Table 6). This target is significantly higher than the existing NECP. The NECP 2040 GHG emission reduction target is set at -82% without LULUCF and can reach -87% with LULUCF. The corresponding target for 2050 is set, according to the scenario simulated, at -93% without LULUCF and -99% with LULUCF, a performance marginally close to the 2050 climate neutrality objective. As will be seen below, there are still small emissions in 2050 in some sectors which are difficult to fully eliminate. These emissions need to be compensated through negative emissions (i.e. via GHG storage that reduces the condensation of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere) and absorption, under the LU-LUCF.

Table 6. Climate targets of Greece in the NECP 2023 (2025-2050) (Hellenic Republic Ministry of Environment and Energy, 2023)

NECP (Apr 2023)	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
GHG, without LULUCF (change since 1990 in %)	-41	-54	-68	-82	-89	-93
GHG, with LULUCF (change since 1990 in %)	-44	-57	-72	-87	-95	-99
RES as % of gross final energy consumption	31	44	65	83	97	105
Energy efficiency, %	-4	-5	-14	-18	-22	-27

Among Greece's main positive elements EC mentioned that „on decarbonisation, the plan outlines the

of carbon removal technologies such as Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) and provides projections of expected capacities for capture, storage and use up to 2050" (European Commission, 2024).

	2030 value submitted in the draft updated NECP	2030 target indicated by EU level legislation	Assessment of 2030 ambition
Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in ESR sectors (compared with 2005)	N/A	-22.7%*	No projections provided in the plan, but Greece would overachieve based on its nationally net -46% target for ESR sectors
GHG emissions in LULUCF (Mt CO ₂ eq. net GHG removals)	-4.8	-1.154 (additional removals target) -4.373 (total net removals)**	Greece is projecting to meet the target
Energy Efficiency (final energy consumption)	15.4 Mtoe	14.6 Mtoe***	Greece's final energy consumption is above the indicated target resulting from EU legislation
Renewable Energy (share of renewable energy in gross final consumption)	44%	39%****	Greece's submitted contribution to the EU target is significantly above the one resulting from EU legislation

* under the Effort Sharing Regulation (ESR).
 ** under the Regulation on Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF).
 *** according to the formula set out in Annex I of the Directive (EU) 2023/1791 on energy efficiency and amending Regulation (EU) 2023/955 ('EED recast').
 **** according to the formula set out in Annex II of the Regulation (EU) 2018/1999 on the Governance Regulation of the Energy Union and Climate Action.

Fig. 8 _ Greece's key objectives and contributions (European Commission, 2024)

The following comments provided by EC:

- 1) The plan does not provide separate projections for greenhouse gas emissions under the Effort Sharing Regulation (ESR), which is essential to assess the likelihood for the draft updated plan to reach the ESR target of -22.7% in 2030 below 2005 levels (Fig. 8). Projections under Article 18 of the Governance Regulation that Greece submitted in March 2023 include a WEM scenario for the ESR sectors expecting 2030 emissions of -35.5% compared to 2005 levels, significantly below the ESR target.
- 2) The draft updated plan outlines the importance of carbon removal technologies, such as Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS), and provides projections of expected capacities for capture, storage and use up to 2050, but does not describe a detailed plan or the necessary funding to get there.

In the draft NECP review CCUS is included as number 9 among 10 measures for strategic priorities:

- Innovation and systemic solutions in CCUS for the energy transition of the country's industry (mainly water production, oil refining, and fertiliser manufacturing).
- Development of investments for the capture of CO₂ from industrial processes, its use in the production of synthetic fuels, the future development of climate-neutral CO₂ capture technologies and the development of CO₂ geological storage infrastructure.

CCUS Projects (Hellenic Republic Ministry of Environment and Energy, 2023):

CO₂ capture from industry is the fastest way to reduce the CO₂ emissions in this sector. Captured CO₂ may be used for production of synthetic fuels by 2040 in line with EU policy.

The investment facility for CO₂ capture emitted by industrial installations, including refineries and cement factories is considered.

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Two projects have already been approved for co-financing by the Innovation Fund: an IRIS project for CO₂ capture at the H₂ production plant of a refinery in Corinth, and an IFESTOS project for CO₂ capture in a cement plant in Viotia. The first CO₂ storage plant in Prinos, Kavala, is already covered by the Recovery and Resilience Fund for co-financing. The plant will have a capacity to capture 2,5 Mt of CO₂ annually in full operation. It is estimated that the first phase (capacity of around 1 Mt CO₂ per year) will be ready by the end of 2025 and the full capacity second phase (by the end of 2027).

The completion of regulatory framework for the CCUS is also progressing. Responsibility for supervising the construction and operation of CCUS projects has been assigned to a specialised public-limited company (EDEYEP).

Finally, CCS technologies are expected to be used also in the maritime sector. Recent decisions by the IMO (IMO/MEPC 80, July 2023) on binding GHGE reduction targets, including the 2050 Maritime Decarbonisation (net zero) target and the interim but ambitious absolute GHGE reduction targets in 2030 and 2040 make CCS technology an important solution for shipping. It is considered that captured CO₂ using CCS onboard technology may be used as a feedstock to produce alternative fuels with recycled carbon such as blue methanol.

EC assessment on CCUS (European Commission, 2024):

- 1) The plan identifies CCUS as one of several strategic priorities. It aims in the short term to create a CCS value chain in Greece that will mainly help to hard-to-abate industries and processes (water production, oil refinery, fertiliser, and alternative fuels manufacturing) but also in shipping.
- 2) In terms of projections of potential CO₂ capture volumes, the plan indicates that:
 - 0.932 Mt of CO₂ will be captured annually by 2035,
 - 3.287 Mt by 2040,
 - 3.447 Mt by 2045,
 - 3.653 Mt of CO₂ will be captured annually by 2050.
- 3) It is not clear how much CO₂ will be captured from biogenic sources. While no precise estimations have been made for 2030, it is mentioned that industrial emissions that could be captured and stored may reach 15 million tonnes per year as early as 2030.
- 4) Estimations of available CO₂ storage capacity have been made for
 - 2040 (4.363 Mt/yr.)
 - 2045 (4.577 Mt/yr.)
 - 2050 (5.395 Mt/yr.)
- 5) For 2030 and 2035, estimations will be reviewed based on the progress of the Prinos CO₂ storage site, which is strongly related to the timetables of selected Innovation Fund projects in Greece (the IRIS project in Corinth, and the IFESTOS project in Viotia).
- 6) Prinos, the first CO₂ storage plant in Prino, Kavala, is already covered by the Recovery and Resilience Fund for co-financing. The plant will have a capacity to absorb 2,5 million tonnes of CO₂ per year in full operation. It is estimated that the first phase (for a capacity of about 1 Mt per year) will be completed by the end of 2025 and the second phase (full capacity) by the end of 2027.
- 7) The completion of the relevant regulatory framework for CCUS of CO₂ is also reported to be progressing. The plan does not provide details on how the CO₂ will be transported. The importance of BECCS and DACCS technologies is noted, and their use is considered. The technologies are under development; however, no detailed plans are outlined.

5.2.3 SUMMARY FOR GREECE

Paris Climate Agreement

Greece has ratified the Paris Climate Agreement on 14 Oct 2016.

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CO₂ emissions

In Greece, total fossil CO₂ emissions decreased from 77.9 Mt in 1990 to 56.78 Mt in 2022. CO₂ emissions per capita in Greece decreased from 9.17 t in 2005 (maximum since 1990) to 5.14 t in 2022 (Table 2).

The largest CO₂ in Greece are power plants, refineries, and cement plants.

Climate and energy strategic targets

According to EU NDC submitted in October 2023 and Regulation (EU) 2023/857 sets an EU-level greenhouse gas emission reduction target of 40% by 2030, compared to 2005, for the sectors that it covers. Greece has greenhouse gas emission reduction target of 22.7% by 2030, compared to 2005. Strategic targets to decrease GHG emissions compared to 1990 in the revised draft 2023:

- 1) by 2030: -54% excluding LULUCF CO₂ removals, and -57% with LULUCF. This target is significantly higher than the existing NECP.
- 2) by 2040 -82% without LULUCF and -87% with LULUCF.
- 3) for 2050 -93% without LULUCF and -99% with LULUCF,

Small emissions in 2050 in some sectors which are difficult to fully eliminate need to be compensated through negative emissions and CCS technology.

London Protocol

Greece is a member of the London Convention but has not yet ratified the London Protocol and did not report on plans to do it.

OSPAR Convention

Greece is a party of the OSPAR Convention under the European Union sign (Table 3.1).

BARCELONA Convention

Greece is a member of the Barcelona Convention for the Protection of the Mediterranean Sea Against Pollution. Its Protocol, amended in 1995, prohibits all dumping activities with some exceptions, where CO₂ is not yet included. However, the 1995 amendment is not yet in force, and by now CO₂ injection offshore is not prohibited.

EU CCS Directive

In Greece, the Ministerial Decision 48416/2037/E.103/2011 (Government Gazette B' 2516/2011), as amended, transposed the CCS Directive 2009/31/EC into Greek law. The decision largely follows the philosophy of the EU CCS Directive.

The recent law L.4920/2022 (art.228 par.1), as amended by L.4964/2022 (Article 175), designates the Hellenic Hydrocarbons and Energy Resources Management Company (HEREMA) as the competent authority for the licensing, monitoring, and supervision of carbon storage projects. Moreover, Article 173 of L.4964/2022 introduces a new licensing process for CO₂ exploration and storage permits for economical operators who already hold hydrocarbon exploration and production rights in areas which could potentially be used for carbon storage (HEREMA, 2023).

Prospects for CO₂ storage

Greece has very good geological options for the storage of CO₂ emissions.

CO₂ storage capacity

In the EUGeoCapacity project different potential sites for CO₂ storage in Greece with total storage capacity in deep saline aquifers and hydrocarbon fields of 2190 Mt were reported. The total effective storage capacity in aquifers alone in Greece was estimated to be around 184 Mt (Vangkilde-Pedersen,

T. et al. 2009, Hatziyannis, 2009). This CO₂ storage capacity concerns the Tertiary sedimentary basins of Prinos, West Thessaloniki and a part of the Mesohellenic Trough (Hatziyannis, 2009). CO₂ storage capacity in the Miocene Pentalofos formation was estimated recently as 1435 Gt CO₂ (Koukouzas and Gemeni, 2019).

Transboundary issues

In 2023 Greece reported to the EC: „There is no experience with transboundary CO₂ transport and no plans for cross-border CO₂ storage sites or complexes. The planned Prinos CO₂ storage project is planned to be the only available storage site for the regional industrial emitters in hard-to-abate sectors. As its suitability for CO₂ storage is confirmed, it is expected that it could receive CO₂ from other EU emitters outside Greece via ships (e.g., from Italy)”. (HEREMA, 2023).

National CO₂ Tax

Greece has not introduced a national Carbon Tax yet.

Greek policymakers answered “Maybe” to the Question about national CO₂ tax in the questionnaire: *(If Greece does not have enough financial capacity to support national CCUS clusters and hubs, could a national CO₂ tax be introduced to address this issue?)*

6 POLICY MAKERS QUESTIONNAIRE ON CCUS

In the framework of the HERCCULES project, this questionnaire is intended to investigate the policymakers' approach concerning the international and national CCUS regulations influencing the implementation of CCUS cluster projects and hubs in targeted regions (London Protocol, EU CCS Directive, EU ETS Directive, etc), as well as the regulatory situation and the political strategies for implementing integrated-chain CCUS at European, national (IT, EL) and regional level.

6.1 ITALIAN CASE

Six policymakers answered the Italian questionnaire. The questions and answers are included in the following sections.

6.1.1 CLIMATE STRATEGIES

In Italy, the CCUS is included in the Integrated National Energy and Climate Plan (PNIEC, in Italian) which sets national targets for 2030 on energy efficiency, renewables and CO₂ emissions reduction, as well as those on energy security, interconnections, the single energy market and competitiveness, development and sustainable mobility. The path set out by the PNIEC allows almost all EU environmental and climate targets to be met by 2030, in some cases exceeding them.

2. 1) *Do you expect that CCUS will be implemented in Italy on a wider industrial scale by 2050?*

Options to answer:

- Yes
- No

N	Answer to question 1. 1)
1	Yes

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2	Yes
3	Yes
4	No
5	Yes
6	Yes

1) Does your government actively work on supporting CCUS cluster and hub projects in Italy?

Options to answer:

- Yes
- No

N	Answer to question 2)
1	Yes
2	Yes
3	I do not know
4	I do not know
5	No
6	No

2) a. If you answered **NO** to question 2), please describe the obstacles. b. If you answered **YES** to question 2), please describe how the Italian government is actively working in the CCUS field.

No	Answer to questions 2) a and b
1	Italian policy on CCUS has been inconsistent. Research funding has been available for years, and Italy, through the MUR, has joined the European consortium ECCSEL ERIC (the European Research Infrastructure for CO ₂ Capture, Utilization, Transport and Storage). Despite the funds provided by ECCSEL, political interest in CCUS declined around 2015. Interest has recently revived, partly due to ENI's industrial project.
2	The PNIEC, which was remodelled in 2023 and sent to the Commission, confirms that achieving the goal of curbing emissions, particularly from the industrial sector, will also require the use of CO ₂ capture and storage/utilization. Specific targets for CO ₂ capture and storage will, to this end, be set based on the geological CO ₂ storage capacity that can be made operationally available by 2030 and beyond, from the utilization of depleted offshore gas fields, currently estimated at more than 500 million tons for depleted or depleting gas fields alone in the Central Adriatic offshore. It is planned to update and simplify the rules governing this activity in Italy, which were enacted to implement Directive 2009/31/EC.
3	As part of PNIEC 2023, Italy's goals are to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and implement hubs for CCUS. Italy, along with other Mediterranean countries is also collaborating on transnational projects for CO ₂ storage. However, the funding needed for CCUS technologies is likely to be undersized to real needs.
4	N/A
5	It seems that among the priorities in terms of abating CO ₂ emissions, Italy assigns almost no role to CCUS, while still supporting research, especially concerning infrastructure.
6	Lack of funds to finance applied research to develop CCUS technologies in different industries and dedicated infrastructure; lack of experiments to combine CCUS with NBS solutions. There is a lack of regulations for authorization pathways; in fact, ENI and SAM's CCS project for Ravenna are rubricated as "experimental" despite adopting established techniques in northern Europe.

6.1.2 INTERNATIONAL CCS REGULATIONS - THE LONDON PROTOCOL

The main regulatory instrument internationally for pollution caused by the dumping of waste and substances is the London Protocol (LP) or Protocol 96, ratified in 1996, which amends the text of the previous London Convention adopted in 1972 and entered into force in 1975. The LP permits the submersion of CO₂ streams in the seabed for storage in underwater geological formations.

The following implementations have been appointed to the 1996 original text: In **2006**, the LP Contracting Parties adopted amendments to Annex 1 of the LP to regulate carbon capture and sequestration in sub-sea geological formations (CCS-SSGF).

In **2009**, the Parties amended LP Article 6 concerning the export of wastes for dumping purposes, aimed at enabling Parties to share transboundary sub-seabed geological formations for CO₂ storage projects.

In **2019**, Contracting Parties to the London Protocol adopted a resolution (LP.5(14)) to allow the provisional application of an amendment to Article 6 of the Protocol to allow the export of CO₂ for storage in SSGF. Two or more countries can agree to export CO₂ for geological storage.

Since 2006 Italy has been a member of the London Protocol, however, it seems that it has not yet implemented the amendment to Article 6 that allows the export of CO₂ for offshore storage under the seabed.¹

3) *What is the current status of discussions regarding the execution of Article 6 of the London Protocol, which would authorize the import and export of CO₂ for storage under the seabed?*

Options to answer:

- Highly implemented
- Implemented
- It is a work in progress
- It is on the government agenda but has not yet been discussed
- I do not know

No	Answer to question 3)
1	I do not know
2	It is a work in progress
3	It is a work in progress
4	I do not know
5	It has been put on the agenda by the government but has not yet been discussed
6	It has been put on the agenda by the government but has not yet been discussed

3b) *If you wish, please explain your answer to question 3.*

No	Answer to question 3b)
1	I have no information on this.
2	Italy plans to develop CCS technology. Alongside France and Greece, they have created and submitted a regional scheme to bolster CCS infrastructure development in the Mediterranean Sea basin under the TEN-E Regulation, in March 2023. The pan-national plan is flexible and supports the growth of CCS value chains, enabling the promotion of further projects within the

	area. Consequently, additional countries located along the Mediterranean may join at a later stage to enhance regional CCS collaboration.
3	Italy is involved in several Projects of Common Interest (PCI), such as "Callisto Mediterranean CO2 Network," "Augusta C2," and "Prinos CO2 storage," which will start in the coming years, between 2025 and 2035. Nationally, for years the Italian government has been funding important research infrastructures such as the ZECOMIX plant operated by the ENEA Casaccia Research Center.
4	NA
5	As with the previous question, it is not a priority issue for Italy, see also the absence of projects where the CCUS supply chain is applied even as a pilot, except for the Ravenna Hub, which, however, is all paid for by ENI.
6	The June 2023 PNIEC states the intention to "file a formal declaration of provisional application of the 2009 amendment to Article 6 of the London Protocol and initiate discussions with France and Greece to conclude bilateral agreements on transboundary CO2 transport to develop permanent geological storage projects under the seabed."

4) *How does Italy intend to permit the import and export of CO₂ for offshore storage under the seabed, if at all?*

N	Answer to question 4
1	Currently, there are no reports detailing specific strategies for the handling of CO ₂ imports intended for offshore geological storage.
2	I am not aware of the development of the various methodologies
3	Italy should allow it, within the scope of the PCI projects in which he is scheduled to participate.
4	N/A
5	I don't know
6	See the previous answer

6.1.3 NATIONAL CCS REGULATIONS

In compliance with Italian Legislative Decree No. 162 of 14 September 2011, which implements Directive 2009/31/EC, Italy allows for CO₂ storage in areas not affected by aquifers that provide water for drinking or irrigation, as well as in non-seismic areas (Art. 7 points 9 and 10).

5) According to national CCS regulations, CO₂ storage is permitted in Italy. From your perspective, are there any regulatory gaps including permitting and monitoring procedures?

Options to answer:

- Yes
- No
- Maybe

N	Answer to question 5
1	Yes
2	Maybe
3	Yes
4	Maybe
5	Yes
6	Yes

8. If you answered YES to question 5), please explain.

N	Explanation to answer YES of the question 5
1	Currently, according to the existing regulations, CO ₂ geological confinement is only permitted if there are extraction permits in place. This is exemplified by ENI's Ravenna project, which involves the confinement of CO ₂ in a depleted gas field. However, there are no procedures for obtaining permits for other types of confinement sites.
2	NA
3	Monitoring and permitting attitudes need to be more clearly defined by the legislature, along with the implementation of better-defined regulatory procedures.
4	NA
5	The current legislation concerns permit for exploration and exploitation related to hydrocarbons. The 2009 European directive, after an initial initiative, which led to the establishment of a consultation table with all stakeholders (industry, research and ministries), to transform the directive into implementing decrees, the topic was no longer addressed. The reason was mainly to issues related to the geology of the Italian territory (see earthquakes and areas of high seismicity and other natural hazards) but also to problems of public acceptance.
6	Still missing is the decree required under Article 7, c.1 to identify the areas of the national territory and the exclusive economic zone within which storage sites may be selected under this decree and the areas in which storage is not permitted. In fact, with DL 181/2023, a sentence was inserted in c.3 to provide for the issuance of licenses for experimental programs in depleted hydrocarbon reservoirs located in the territorial sea.

6.1.4 ECONOMY- EU ETS

Comprehensive carbon pricing can provide: (1) across-the-board incentives for energy conservation and shifting to cleaner fuels, (2) substantial government revenue; (3) substantial domestic environmental gains (e.g., fewer local air pollution deaths). The first carbon tax ever introduced was in Finland, in 1990. A carbon tax introduced in Norway in 1991 has been successful in incentivising the development of the Sleipner and Snohvit CCS projects. At US\$17/tCO₂, the cost of injecting and storing CO₂ for the Sleipner project was much less than the US\$50/tCO₂ tax penalty at the time for CO₂ vented to the atmosphere. This was complemented by a commercial need to separate the CO₂ from natural gas to meet market requirements and provided a clear business case to invest in CCS (<https://www.imf.org/en/Publications/Policy-Papers/Issues/2019/05/01/Fiscal-Policies-for-Paris-Climate-Strategies-from-Principle-to-Practice-46826>).

9. 6) *Is there financial support available on a national level for research, development, and innovation projects related to CCUS in Italy?*

Options to answer:

- Yes
- No
- Maybe
- No, but it is on the Agenda

No	Answer to question 6
1	Yes
2	Yes
3	Maybe
4	Yes
5	Yes
6	No, but it is on the Agenda

7) *What are the main challenges and obstacles to receiving governmental aid for the development of CCUS clusters in Italy?*

No	Answer to question 7
1	Several research funding programs exist, although there is currently a lack of real coordination of activities. Relative to industrial applications, the resources available today are limited.
2	It is essential to establish and advance coherent regulatory measures that align decarbonisation, economic competitiveness and employment facets via integrated planning and supporting mechanisms for risk reduction across the entire supply chain.
3	In Europe, the renewables-electricity pair remains predominant for decarbonization targets, yet these are only part of achieving net-zero targets, especially in those areas where their implementation cannot deliver the expected results. CCUS must be complementary to other technologies to work on for the green transition.
4	N/A
5	Always the same reason, it is not a priority issue.
6	Absence of a national carbon tax

8) *Is it possible to use accommodated CO₂ taxes from EU ETS for this purpose?*

Options to answer:

- Yes
- No
- Maybe
- I do not know

No	Answer to question 8
1	No
2	Yes
3	Yes
4	I do not know
5	I do not know
6	I do not know

9) If Italy does not have enough financial capacity to support national CCUS clusters and hubs, could a national CO₂ tax be introduced to address this issue?

Options to answer:

- Yes
- No
- Maybe

No	Answer to question 9
1	Yes
2	Maybe
3	Yes
4	Maybe
5	Maybe
6	Yes

6.1.5 INFRASTRUCTURE (TO OIL COMPANIES AND MINISTERS)

Italy has the infrastructure of the oil and gas industry.

10) What plans do you have for developing CCS infrastructure and potential reuse, such as pipelines for transporting CO₂?

No	Answer to question 10
1	There are currently no national plans. There is ENI's plan for the Ravenna hub, to which are added several experimental studies on transportation materials, including the repurposing of existing pipelines for natural gas.
2	A recent study (Ambrosetti, 2023), places in the hands of the future Ravenna hub, the ability for Italy to achieve neutrality goals, while creating Added Value, not affecting the economic vitality of the Hard to abate sectors, and creating the possibility for Italy to fully join the London Protocol network
3	CO ₂ pipelines are planned to be developed into a comprehensive network, connecting emitters and storage sites throughout the country and with neighbouring countries

4	At the regional level we do not have this type of information
5	There are many European projects studying the use of existing infrastructure to transport CO ₂ . For Italy not being able to field an operational project, it is difficult to participate and initiate a feasibility study.
6	SNAM has been thinking about the regeneration of existing national pipeline infrastructure.

6.1.6 NATIONAL AND LOCAL PERMITS (TO NATIONAL AND LOCAL AUTHORITIES)

Oil and gas pipelines and wells could potentially be repurposed for transporting and storing CO₂. While this can result in cost savings, reusing existing infrastructure does carry some risks, including the possibility of leakage and CO₂ corrosion. Several projects are currently underway to assess the viability of using pipelines and wells for large-scale CO₂ storage (for more information see "Can Oil Wells Be Reused for CO₂ Storage?" and ZEP, 2020, A Trans-European CO₂ Transportation Infrastructure for CCUS: Opportunities & Challenges).

In Italy, the oil and gas licences are owned by private companies.

11) Do you expect any challenges regarding CCUS?

Options to answer:

- Yes
- No
- Maybe

N	Answer to question 11
1	Yes
2	Maybe
3	Maybe
4	Yes
5	Maybe
6	Yes

12) Do current regulations allow to give permits for CCUS to the oil and gas license owners?

N	Answer to question 12
1	Yes
2	Maybe
3	Yes
4	Yes
5	No
6	Yes

6.2 GREECE CASE

Only two policymakers from Greece answered the questions, despite several times repeated e-mails and calls from the HERCCULES partners to the higher number of the stakeholders.

6.2.1 CLIMATE STRATEGIES

In Greece, the National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP) sets the national targets for 2030 on energy efficiency, renewables, and CO₂ emissions reduction, as well as those on energy security, interconnections, the single energy market and competitiveness, development and sustainable mobility.

Although there is not a specific legislative framework for CO₂ transportation, some aspects are covered by the National Joint Ministerial Decision 48416/2037/2011 E. 103 and the Joint Ministerial Decision 181478/965 of 2017.

1) *What is the role and place of CO₂ capture, utilisation and storage technology in national climate mitigation strategy and policy compared to other green technologies?*

N	Answer to question 1
1	In Greece, CO ₂ capture, utilization and storage interventions are currently low on the list of priorities for combating climate change. However, the National Energy and Climate Plan issued in December 2019 contains in chapter 3.8 "Research and innovation" (p. 232, FP6.6), the development of innovative energy storage applications as well as CO ₂ capture, storage and use technologies, as one of the 11 Policy Priorities. Moreover, the same text is included in Table 27: "Policy measures foreseen for the promotion of Research, Innovation and Competitiveness"
2	Although it has been defined in the National Energy and Climate Plan as one of the 11 Policy Priorities, at the moment, CO ₂ capture, utilization and storage technology does not seem to be a priority in the national strategy compared to other green technologies.

2) *Do you expect that CCUS will be implemented in Greece in a wider industrial scale by 2050?*

Options to answer:

- Yes
- No
- I do not know

No	Answer to question 2
1	Yes
2	I do not know

3) *Does your government actively work on supporting CCUS cluster and hub projects in Greece?*

Options to answer:

- Yes

- No
- Maybe

No	Answer to question 3
1	Yes
2	Maybe

4. a. If you answered NO to question 3), please describe the obstacles.
 b. If you answered YES to question 2), please describe how the Greek government is actively working in the CCUS field.

N	Answer to questions 3a and 2b
1	<p>As things stand, it cannot be clearly established that CCUS will be deployed on a large industrial scale by 2050. However, the fact that this technology is increasingly disseminated based on the policies of the European Commission and taking into account that it exists in the NECP (as mentioned above) is a first indication of the existence of a framework and will of the Greek state for the broad industrial development of innovative technology. Besides, from 2011 until today, several things have been done in this direction. Specifically, according to HEREMA research:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2011: With the Greek State as the sole shareholder, the Hellenic Hydrocarbons Management Company S.A. (HHRM) manages national interests related to the exploration and production of hydrocarbons, with particular emphasis on natural gas • 2011: Greece transposed the CCS Directive into national law by Joint Ministerial Decision (JMD Government Gazette B 2516_2011) • 2020: HHRM begins its transformation by strengthening ESG standards and exploring synergies between various energy sectors towards a more sustainable future • 2022: HHRM is renamed Hellenic Hydrocarbons and Energy Resources Management Company (HHRM) and expanded its responsibilities to include the licensing of underground storage of natural gas (including CO₂, natural gas and hydrogen) and offshore wind farms (Article 228 of Law 4920/2022) • 2022: Operators holding a right or license to find and exploit hydrocarbons in a specific area have the right to apply for a permit to store CO₂ in the same area if proven suitable. • 2022: EDEYEP grants the first exploration license to Energean for the Prinos deposit (Government Gazette B 5247_2022) • EDEYEP was appointed as the implementing body of Subproject 2 of Axis 3-1.3 "Transition to a green and sustainable transport system – Support for green production and transport – development of carbon capture and storage technology"
2	NA

6.2.2 INTERNATIONAL CCS REGULATIONS - THE LONDON PROTOCOL

However, Greece seems not to be a member of the London Protocol (Later remark from HERCCULES WP8 – Greece is a London Convention party, but still is not a member of the London Protocol).

5. 4) *What is the state of discussion regarding Greece's membership of the London Protocol?*
 Options to answer:

- It is about to be implemented
- It is a work in progress
- It is on the government agenda but has not been discussed yet
- It is not currently on the government agenda

- I do not know

N	Answer to question 5. 4)
1	I do not know
2	It's ongoing

6. 4b) If you wish, please explain your answer to question 4.

N	Answer to question .6 4b)
1	There are currently no published data on Greece's accession to the London Protocol. However, following the policy of the other European countries as usual, I suspect that it is going to join to be able to participate in the CO ₂ trade in the future.
2	Greece has been a member of the London Protocol since 1996. I do not know whether it also adopted the subsequent resolutions that you say were carried out in 2006, 2009 and 2019.

7. 5) In the event of non-membership, how does Greece intend to support the cross-border export and import of CO₂, if at all?

N	Answer to question 7. 5)
1	I consider this possibility very difficult, as on these issues Greece follows the strategy of the European Union.
2	Greece is already integrated.

6.2.3 NATIONAL CCS REGULATIONS

In compliance with the national Joint Ministerial Decision 48416/2037/2011 E. 103, which implements Directive 2009/31/EC, Greece allows for CO₂ storage.

8. 6) *According to national CCS regulations, CO₂ storage is permitted in Greece. perspective, are there any regulatory gaps including permitting and monitoring procedures?*

Options to answer:

- Yes
 No
 Maybe

N	Answer to question 8. 6)
1	Yes
2	Maybe

9. If you answered **YES** to question 6), please provide an explanation.

No	Answer to question 9.
1	In Greece, the only licensed storage facility for CO ₂ emissions is the Prinos reservoir. Recently, with the legislation of 2022, EDEYEP was designated as the licensing authority for the exploration and investment of underground or underwater reservoir conversion (usually old,

	depleted hydrocarbon deposits). However, secondary legislation is pending, such as storage fees and how the state will also derive revenue from the concession of storage space.
2	So far only one permit has been granted and the CCS project has not yet taken place. So we cannot be aware of possible gaps and difficulties in permitting and monitoring the process.

6.2.4 ECONOMY- EU ETS

10. 7) *Is there financial support available on a national level for research, development, and innovation projects related to CCUS in Greece?*

Options to answer:

- Yes
- No
- Maybe
- No, but it is on the Agenda

N Answer to question 10. 7)	
1	No, but it is on the agenda
2	No, but it is on the agenda

11. 8) What are the main challenges and obstacles to receiving governmental aid for the development of CCUS clusters in Greece?

N Answer to question 11. 8)	
1	So far, research and development efforts related to CCUS are funded by European programs and with the participation of state resources. The National Energy and Climate Plan includes in the chapter research and innovation, the development of innovative energy storage applications as well as technologies for capturing, storing and using CO ₂ . Under this plan, state financial support is foreseen for research and development projects of carbon capture and storage technology in Greece. CCUS technology needs to move up the hierarchy of the government's agenda. At the moment, the dominant trends are the installation of power plants from RES, energy saving and dependence on fossil fuels.
2	The development of CCUS in Greece is not yet a priority. However, the new National Energy and Climate Plan includes in the chapter research and innovation, the development of innovative energy storage applications as well as technologies for capturing, storing and using CO ₂ . Under this plan, state financial support is foreseen for research and development projects of carbon capture and storage technology in Greece.

12. 9) Is it possible to use accommodated CO₂ taxes from EU ETS for this purpose?

Options to answer:

- Yes
- No
- Maybe
- I do not know

No Answer to question 12. 9)	
1	Maybe
2	Maybe

13. 10) If Greece encounters financial challenges in sustaining national CCUS clusters and hubs, could the implementation of a national CO₂ tax, as already done in more advanced CCUS countries, be a viable solution?

No	Answer to question 13. 10)
1	Maybe
2	Maybe

6.2.5 INFRASTRUCTURE (TO OIL COMPANIES AND MINISTERS)

Greece has the infrastructure of the oil and gas industry.

14. 11) *What plans do you have for developing CCS infrastructure and potential reuse, such as pipelines for transporting CO₂?*

No	Answer to question 14. 11)
1	There is currently no pipeline network that is not used and could be used to transport CO ₂ . A new pipeline network will have to be built.
2	There is currently no national plan. The creation of a CO ₂ pipeline network requires very large CCS projects which are not currently expected.

6.2.6 NATIONAL AND LOCAL PERMITS (TO NATIONAL AND LOCAL AUTHORITIES)

In Greece, the oil and gas licences are owned by the country.

15. 12) *Do you expect any challenges regarding CCUS?*

Options to answer:

- Yes
- No
- Maybe

No	Answer to question 15. 12)
1	Maybe
2	Maybe

16. 13) Do current regulations allow to give permits for CCUS to the oil and gas license owners?

Options to answer:

- Yes
- No
- Maybe

No	Answer to question 15. 12)
1	Maybe
2	Yes

7 CONCLUSIONS

- Italy and Greece have good prospects for wide industrial implementation of CCUS technology and becoming climate-neutral by 2050. In both countries total CO₂ emissions and emissions per capita significantly decreased by 2022 compared to 1990 and 2005.
- In the NECP 2023 Greece reported to the EC ambitious climate targets, which are mostly in line with EC plans, or even higher, while in the Italian NECP 2023, some targets were lower than required by EC. However, the target for ESR emissions for Greece is lower than the EC requires.
- Both countries implemented the EU CCS Directive to the full extent that permitted CO₂ geological storage and recently made some needed updates and changes. However, there are some areas where additional improvements and regulatory developments should be additionally made in Greece, such as transboundary issues and third-party access to the storage sites.
- National CO₂ storage capacity estimated in research projects and publications is high enough in both countries, however, Italy decided to start with depleted gas fields and exploit at least 500 Mt of their capacity, while Greece's national authorities are only planning to estimate their capacity and considered three options for storage media.
- Concerning international regulations, Italy is in a more advanced situation, as it is a party to the London Protocol and planning to implement an amendment to Article 6, permitting CO₂ export for storage under the seabed. Greece is a part of the London Convention, but not of the Protocol and did not report any plans in this direction.
- Both Italy and Greece did not implement national CO₂ tax and politicians answered either positively or "maybe" that this instrument could be helpful.
- More Italian policy makers participated in the questionnaire survey. It was noticed that they were better informed regarding regulatory issues and national plans than the Greek policymakers. A higher percentage of Italian politicians gave positive answers about possibility to implement industrial scale CCUS and CCS related regulations as compared to negative or uncertain answers.
- Some policymakers from both countries mentioned in their answers that CCUS is not yet a priority in their country.
- In 2023 Greece submitted a national report to the EC about EU CCS Directive updates and application, while Italy was one of two EU countries which did not submit the report. However, in December 2023 Italy published regulation "Decreto Energia" in Gazzetta Ufficiale, composed of 21 parts, where CCS regulation was updated mostly about authorization process and experimental CO₂ storage, but not only, in the extensive part 7 of this law.

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